

Proceedings of 3rd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2024)

(MAY 29-31, 2024)

Jointly Organized By

Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP

(Estd.25 Aug 1969 - (Affiliated To D.D.U. Gorakhpur University Gorakhpur(U.P.) | B++ with C.G.P.A. 2.84)

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Science Tech Institute, Lucknow UP

(Run by: Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society)

(Registered by : Govt. of U.P & Ordinance No. 21 of 1860, Reg. No. LUC/03140/2019-2020, INDIA)

(Registered by: : Govt. of India , NITI Aayog, Reg. No. UP/2019/0248444)

दिविजयनाथ स्नातकोत्तर महाविद्यालय, गोरखपुर
शिक्षकगण

Edited by

Prof. (Dr.) Parikshit Singh

Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh

Dr. Dharmendra Kumar Yadav

**Proceeding of 3rd International Conference on Advance
Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2024)**

Editors

Prof.(Dr.) Parikshit Singh

Professor

Dept. of Botany
Digvijay Nath P.G College
Gorakhpur, UP, India

Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh

General Secretary

MKSES Educational Society,
Lucknow, UP, India

Dr. Dharmendra Kumar Yadav

Assistant Professor

Department of Statistics & Demography
NIHFW, New Delhi

3rd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2024)

(May 29-31, 2024)

Jointly organized by

Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP

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&

Science Tech Institute

(Run by: Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society)

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(Registered by: Govt. of India, NITI Aayog, Reg. No. UP/2019/0248444)

Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP

Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur was established on 25th August, 1969 by the managing committee constituted under Maharana Pratap Shiksha Parishad, Gorakhpur. It is situated in civil lines, the heart of Gorakhpur city in eastern Uttar Pradesh. Days are not far when the college shall be able to realize the vision and the grand mission of the great soul 'Brahmleen Mahant Digvijai Nath ji Maharaj', whose name decorates the identity of the College. His Holiness 'Brahmleen Mahant Digvijai Nath ji Maharaj, former Head Priest of world fame Shree Guru Goraksh Nath Temple, Gorakhpur was the founder of the college. He was a pioneer of educational renaissance in Eastern U.P. It was none other than himself who established Maha Rana Pratap Shiksha Parishad, Gorakhpur in 1932 to spread the light of knowledge and awareness among the people of Eastern U.P. whom he found to be living in utter poverty, ignorance and backwardness of all kinds. He came to Gorakhnath temple, Gorakhpur at the age of five from the Royal Rana Family of Mewar, Rajasthan in 1900 and grew and learnt the lesson of selfless sacrifice and dedication to the service of humanity under the spiritual care of his accomplished great Guru Yogiraj Gambhir Nathji Maharaj. In 1949-50 Maharana Pratap Degree College was established by "Maharana Pratap Shiksha Parishad Gorakhpur", which was later sacrificed to contribute to the establishment of Gorakhpur University. Maharana Pratap Degree College along with its entire infrastructure including teaching and non-teaching staff was dedicated to count for the resources to meet up the requirements for establishment of the University of Gorakhpur, in 1958. Post-merger of the Maharana Pratap Degree College into Gorakhpur University, there was a vacuum in the educational facilities of the area. To fill in this vacuum, Digvijai Nath College was established on 25th August 1969. Now the administration of this college is run by the managing committee appointed by Maharana Pratap Shiksha Parishad, Gorakhpur, under inspiring guidance and patronage of His Holiness Mahant Aditya Nath ji Maharaj. His holiness Gorakshpeethadheeshwar 'Brahmleen Mahant Avedya Nathji Maharaj (the Ex-Head priest of Gorakhnath Temple) and his worthy successor who is the Chief Minister of Uttar Pradesh His Holiness reverent Yogi Aditya Nath ji Maharaj, is the guiding light behind more than four dozen institutions, including D.N.P.G. College Gorakhpur, successfully run by the Maharana Pratap Shiksha Parishad. The College holds the glory of functioning with four faculty disciplines covering various departments at undergraduate and post graduate levels. College provides education at graduate level in eleven subjects covering Arts, six in Science and Commerce. Post Graduate teaching is offered in Ancient History Archeology & Culture, Geography and Hindi & Modern Indian Language; apart from its renowned Bachelors in Education. In addition to these, part time classes in eight non-practical subjects are also offered and the Institution also serves as an education center of Uttar Pradesh Rajarshi Tandon Open University; and hosts their 26 courses at U.G and P.G. level. In light of letter dated 15 June 2006 from U.P. State Council for Higher Education we revised 'The Self Study Report' on modified format on the basis of guidelines of

NAAC-Bangalore. Digvijai Nath P.G. college, Civil lines, Gorakhpur has been placed on the UGC-NAAC approved list in 2021 with B⁺⁺ grade with C.G.P.A 2.84. Gorakhnath sahyik kendra is established by UP Hindi Sansthan Lucknow in 2019. The institution, guided by the vision of Brahmleen Digvijay Nath Ji Maharaj, is a believer in multi-dimensional development of students. His vision of 'healthy mind residing in a healthy body' is relied and practiced by the Institution. Beyond books and classes students are groomed by extra-curricular and co-curricular activities. Students have participated in Inter-University and Inter-State games & sports as well as in the prestigious republic day parade in the National capital. Students of the college participate and compete with the students of other colleges of Eastern Uttar Pradesh, in different competitions organized during Founder's Week every year from 4th to 10th December. Institution also hosts an annual sports festival. To meet the Post-Accreditation requirements, the College also has the Internal Quality Assurance Cell. IQAC maneuvers to assure the internal quality of Academic and Administrative activities through its different committees at college.

Science Tech Institute, Lucknow UP

(Run by: Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society)

The Science-Tech is one of the premier institutes of Lucknow dedicated to organize various academic activities like conferences, seminars, workshops and training programmes in collaboration with many national & international organizations and Institute have own Publication house and Journals' to be published Edited books, Course books and research papers. The institute is run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow. The society is working for the development of deprived socio-economic students by providing them quality education.

3rd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2024)

Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP are going to organize 3rd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2024). This Conference will provide a platform to the researchers and academicians to enrich their methodological and analytical skills.

This has brought us to a juncture where innovation and interdisciplinary research are crucial for the survival of humanity. It has become a moral imperative these days to have exchange of ideas using available advanced technologies. Hence the global scientific community must become a key player on scientific and technological innovations, but also to impart true education to the academia and industry across the globe. In the era of social distancing, **Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, U.P. & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, U.P.** India has chosen an e-platform for the scientific community to share their ideas and research by organizing a three day **3rd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2024)** Conference will include Keynote lectures, Invited lectures, Oral presentations and Poster presentations.

Chief Patron

Mahanth Yogi Aditya Nath Ji Maharaj, Manager/ Secretary, Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP

Patron

Prof. Udai Pratap Singh, President, Maharana Pratap Siksha Parishad, Gorakhpur, UP, Former Vice Chancellor, V.B.S. Purvanchal University, Jaunpur

❖ Chairperson

Prof.(Dr.).Om Prakash Singh, Principal, Digvijay Nath P.G, College Gorakhpur, UP

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Mrs. Shweta Singh, Chairman, Governing Body, MKSES Educational Society, Lucknow, UP, India

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1. Prof. D.S. Hooda, Former, (Pro-Vice Chancellor) Kurukshetra University, Haryana, India
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3. Prof. Somesh Shukla, Professor Department of Commerce, University of Lucknow, Lucknow
4. Prof. R. K. Shukla (Professor, Department of Physics, University of Lucknow, Lucknow, UP)
5. Prof. C.K. Dixit, Dean & Head, DSMR University, Lucknow, India
6. Prof. R.R. Singh, Professor & Head, D.S.M.N.R.U, Lucknow, UP, India

Convener

- ❖ **Prof.(Dr.) Parikshit Singh**, Professor Dept. of Botany, Digvijay Nath P.G College Gorakhpur, UP, India

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- ❖ **Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh**, General Secretary, Science Tech Institute, MKSES Educational Society Lucknow, UP, India
- ❖ **Dr. Dharmendra Kr. Yadav**, Assistant Professor, Department of Statistics & Demography NIHF, New Delhi

Conference Organizer

- ❖ Dr. Shubhranshu Shekhar Assistant Professor Dept. of Defence and Strategic Studies DNPG College, Gorakhpur
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- ❖ Mr.Jitendra Kumar Pandey, Assistant Professor. Dept. of Geography, Digvijay Nath P.G. College Gorakhpur, UP, India
- ❖ Mr.Rakesh Kumar Singh, Assistant Professor, B.ed. Department, Digvijay Nath PG College Gorakhpur, UP, India
- ❖ Mr.Himanshu Yadav, Assistant Professor, Dept .of Zoology, Digvijay Nath P.G. College Gorakhpur, UP, India
- ❖ Dr. Rashmi Singh, Associate Professor, Amity University, Noida, India
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- ❖ Dr. Uma, Assistant Professor, Dept. of Agronomy, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar University, Agra, U.P.

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 Prof. Ramesh kundal, Government Medical College Patiyala, Panjab, India
 Prof. Somesh Kumar Shukla, University of Lucknow, Lucknow
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 Prof. A.P. Mishra, Sagar University, India

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Prof. D.K. Awasthi, Jai Naryan PG College, Lucknow, UP
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Dr.Mohd. Miya, Shia PG.College, Lucknow, UP, India
Dr. Kaushiki Singh Assistant Professor,Dept. of Commerce, D.SM.N.R.U, Lucknow, UP, India
Dr. Seeta Ram Pal, Assistant Professor, Dept. of Special Education, D.SM.N.R.U, Lucknow, UP, India
Dr. Mahendra Agnihotri, University of Lucknow, Lucknow, UP, India
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Dr. Sushila, K.M Govt. Girls P.G. College, Noida, U.P
Dr. Zeenat Kashmeeri Dada Ramchand Bakhru Sindhu Mahavidyalaya, Nagpur
Dr. Nisha Mani Pandey, KGMU Lucknow, UP, India
Dr. Jahan Ara Karamat Hushain Degree College Lucknow
Dr. Mohd Naseem Siddiqui, Mumtaz P.G.College, Lucknow
Dr. K.C. Dubey, Shia PG College, Lucknow, UP, India
Dr. Tanveer Hasan, Shia PG College, Lucknow, UP, India

Local Advisory Committee

Prof. Shashiprabha Singh, Head of the Department Chemistry, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India
Prof. Dharendra Singh ,Head of the Department History, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India
Prof. Geeta Singh, Head of the Department B.Ed., DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India
Prof. Archana Singh, Head of the Department Sociology, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India
Prof. Satyendra Pratap Singh, Head of the Department Hindi, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India
Dr. Sanjeev Kumar Singh , Head of the Department Commerce DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India
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Dr. Anita Kumari , Head of the Department Zoology, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India
Dr. Nitesh Shukla , Head of the Department Physics, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India
Dr Suraj Kumar Shukla , Head of the Department of Mathematics, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India
Dr. Ram Prasad Yadav, Head of the Department of Defence, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India
Shri Indresh Kumar, Head of the Department of Political Science, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India
Dr. Anil Bhaskar, Head of the Department of Geography, DNPG College, Gorakhpur

UP, India

Dr. Nidhi Rai, Head of the Department of Education, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India

Dr. Piyush Kumar Singh, Head of the Department of English, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India

Dr. Vivek Kumar Shahi, Head of the Department of Psychology, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India

Dr. Pawan Kumar Pandey, Head of the Department of Computer Science, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India

Dr. Harishnkar Gupta, Head of the Department of BCA, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India

Shri Awadhesh Kumar Shukla, Head of the Department of Physical Education, DNPG College, Gorakhpur UP, India

❖ **Awards**

1. **Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society Award for Best Research Presentation “Theme based” (₹1500/- Cash Prize).**

DIGVIJAI NATH POST GRADUATE COLLEGE

GORAKHPUR-273001

(NAAC B⁺⁺ Accredited College)

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website : www.dnngcollege.edu.in

Affiliated to

D.D.U. Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur (U.P.)

Message

It gives me immense pleasure to know that **Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP** are going to organize **3rd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2024) during May 29-31, 2024**. I am sure that this conference will provide a forum to National and International students, Academicians, Researchers and Industrialists to interact and involve in research and innovation. Such academic events benefit the students, teachers and researchers immensely and widen the horizons of their knowledge and work experience in the field of research, analytics and innovation. I sincerely appreciate the humble efforts of the Institute in providing a platform for students, academicians, researchers and industrialists to share their ideas and research outcome through the forum of this Conference. I give my best wishes to all delegates and organizing committee to make this event a grand success.

Prof.(Dr.)Om Prakash Singh
Principal

DIGVIJAI NATH POST GRADUATE COLLEGE

GORAKHPUR-273001

(NAAC B⁺⁺ Accredited College)

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website : www.dnpgcollege.edu.in

Affiliated to

D.D.U. Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur (U.P.)

Message

It gives me immense pleasure to know that **Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP** are going to organize **3rd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2024)**. I am sure that this conference will provide a forum to National and International students, Academicians, Researchers and Industrialists to interact and involve in research and innovation. Such academic events benefit the students, teachers and researchers immensely and widen the horizons of their knowledge and work experience in the field of research, analytics and innovation.

I give my best wishes to all delegates and organizing committee to make this event a grand success.

Prof. Uday Pratap Singh
President

Maharana Pratap Siksha Parishad, Gorakhpur, UP
Former Vice Chancellor
V.B.S. Purvanchal University, Jaunpur

DIGVIJAI NATH POST GRADUATE COLLEGE

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Affiliated to

D.D.U. Gorakhpur University, Gorakhpur (U.P.)

Ref. No. : /2023-24

Date :22-05-2024

Message

I'm incredibly happy to send my greetings on this historic occasion to the core committee of the share that Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP are going to organize 3rd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2024) during May 29-31, 2024. In current scenario interdisciplinary research is foundation of every country and humanity has directly benefited from its results. Interdisciplinary research grounding and education are essential to future competitiveness, because knowledge creation and innovation frequently occur at the interface of disciplines. Inter disciplinary agendas widen the horizon of knowledge and aids to ensure better educational programs. This conference offered opportunity to connect all researchers, scientists and faculties together at one single platform to share their innovative ideas and skills which is helpful to carry out future research in well-organized way.

Prof.(Dr.) Parikshit Singh

Professor

Convenor IQAC

Prof. (Dr) Chandra. K. Dixit,
Dean Faculty Science
Dr. Shakuntala Misra National Rehabilitation University,
Lucknow

Message

It gives me immense pleasure to know that **Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP** are going to organize **3rd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2024)**. I am sure that this conference will provide a forum to national and international students, academicians, researchers and industrialists to interact and involve in Research and Innovation. Such academic events benefit the students, teachers and researchers immensely and widen the horizons of their knowledge and work experience in the field of Research, Analytics and Innovation.

I give my best wishes to all delegates and organizing committee to make this event a grand success.

Date: 24/05/2024

Prof.(Dr.) C. K. Dixit

University of Lucknow
Lucknow, UP, India, 226007

Department of Commerce
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Mobile: 919450378945
Email: Prof.someshshukla@gmail.com

Prof. Somesh Kumar Shukla
Director,
Bhao Rao Devras Shodhpeeth
University of Lucknow,
Lucknow,
UP, India

Message

It gives me immense pleasure to know that **Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP** are going to organize **3rd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2024) during May 29-31, 2024**. I am sure that this conference will provide a forum to national and international students, academicians, researchers and industrialists to interact and involve in Research and Innovation. Such academic events benefit the students, teachers and researchers immensely and widen the horizons of their knowledge and work experience in the field of Research, Analytics and Innovation. I sincerely appreciate the humble efforts of the Institute in providing a platform for students, academicians, researchers and industrialists to share their ideas and research outcome through the forum of this Conference. I give my best wishes to all delegates and organizing committee to make this event a grand success.

Date: 25/05/2024

[Prof. Somesh Kumar Shukla]

लखनऊ विश्वविद्यालय
University of Lucknow

Department of Physics
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Email: rajeshkumarshukla_100@yahoo.com

**Prof. R. K. Shukla,
Professor,
University of Lucknow, UP**

Message

It is indeed matter of great pleasure that the **Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP** are going to organize **3rd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2024) during May 29-31, 2024**. The invited speakers are experts in their area of specialization. I hope that the interaction between various participants will serve as a springboard for newer opportunities and challenges. I am confident that the participants of this conference and students will greatly benefit from attending this meeting and interacting with experts in the field. I compliment organizing committee for this great effort.

Your sincerely

[R. K. Shukla]

Date: 05/05/2024

MANRAJ KUWAR SINGH EDUCATIONAL SOCIETY

(Registered by : Govt. of U.P. & Ordinance No. 21 of 1860)

Reg. Office : Hydell Nahar Chauraha, Housing Society Sarojini Nagar, Lucknow - 226008, UP India

Head Office : 1ST Floor Building No.85 A (Nanak Arcade) Near Shani Mandir,

Parag Road, LDA Colony, Kanpur Road, Lucknow-226012, UP India

Contact No. : +91 9838298016, +91 8299547952 | E-mail : manrajkuwarsec@gmail.com

Mrs. Shweta Singh
Chairman,
MKSES Educational Society
Lucknow, UP, India

Message

It gives me immense pleasure to share that **Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP** are going to organize **3rd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2024) during May 29-31, 2024.**

The conference will offer a great opportunity to discuss important issues, researches and topics from varied fields and will allow exchange of knowledge, ideas.

This conference is also an opportunity to meet virtually many eminent faculty, scholars and public health specialists of national and international repute on a common platform.

I & my team ensure that the audience will experience the exchange of scientific knowledge and return with a satisfactory take home message.

[Shweta Singh]

Date: 05/05/2024

SCIENCE TECH INSTITUTE

(Registered by : Govt. of U.P. Higher Education Department & Ordinance No. 8 of 2002)

Run by : MANRAJ KUWAR SINGH EDUCATIONAL SOCIETY

(Registered by : Govt. of U.P. & Ordinance No. 21 of 1860, Reg. No. LUC/03140/2019-2020)

Reg. Office : Hydell Nahar Chauraha, Housing Society Sarojini Nagar, Lucknow - 226008, UP India

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Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh
General Secretary,
MKSES Educational Society
Lucknow, UP

Message

On behalf of the whole organizing team, share that **Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP** are going to organize **3rd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2024) during May 29-31, 2024.**

I am sure that this online gathering will provide a common platform for academicians of different branches (Medical Sciences, Humanities etc.), public health experts & researchers to put forth their research studies and works.

I take this opportunity to acknowledge all the concerned authorities or persons for their permission, continuous support and guidance in arranging this conference. I am sure that this conference will succeed in the walk on Commerce this path for improving the various soft skills of faculties and students in varied fields.

Date: 23/05/2024

[Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh]

Dr. Neha Singh (PhD, Postdoc)
(Sr. Scientist)
Virology lab, Dept. of Microbiology
Pt. JNM, Medical College, Raipur, C.G. India
Email: nevi0007@gmail.com

Message

I'm incredibly happy to send my greetings on this historic occasion to the core committee of the **share that Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP are going to organize 3rd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2024) during May 29-31, 2024.** In current scenario interdisciplinary research is foundation of every country and humanity has directly benefited from its results. Interdisciplinary research grounding and education are essential to future competitiveness, because knowledge creation and innovation frequently occur at the interface of disciplines. Interdisciplinary agendas widen the horizon of knowledge and aids to ensure better educational programs. This conference offered opportunity to connect all researchers, scientists and faculties together at one single platform to share their innovative ideas and skills which is helpful to carry out future research in well-organized way.

Date:21/05/2024

Dr. Neha Singh

Dr. Dharmendra Kumar Yadav
Assistant Professor
National Institute of Health & Family Welfare
(NIHFW), New Delhi, India
Email: drdkyadav@nihfw.org

Organizing Secretary-ICAIR-23

Message

I feel great pleasure and pride in hosting the **International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2024)** during May 29-31, 2024, organized by **Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP & Science-Tech Institute run by Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow, UP** are going to organize. The conference is envisaged to be a congregation of academicians, researches, practitioners, educators and students. The deliberations and discussions shall enable the participants to take up new challenges and initiatives in the field of interdisciplinary research. We are pleased to present this souvenir to the academic and research community. The abstract of the papers included shall be helpful to chart a road-map in future. I welcome you all in **ICAIR-2024** and hope that your presence turns out to be intellectually stimulating and professionally enriching. I am sure **ICAIR-2024** leaves long lasting memories and a strong legacy to emulate.

Date:25/05/2024

[D. K. Yadav]

Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP

(Estd.25 Aug 1969 - (Affiliated To D.D.U. Gorakhpur University Gorakhpur (U.P.) | B++ with C.G.P.A. 2.84)

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Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research (ICAIR-2024)

Details of Program

ScheduleDAY-1

(29th May 2024)

For Technical Support Contact

Dr. Susheel Kumar Singh (8299547952)

Dr. Dharmendra Kumar Yadav (8840112492)

WhatsApp group Chat link: <https://chat.whatsapp.com/LiFuFEPMDT96bFzETfM4Jq>

Inaugural Session Hosted by: Dr. Dharmendra Kumar Yadav	
Zoom link: https://us02web.zoom.us/j/89099518493?pwd=DWbSm4gSifCgXq0mQxW7ZC0GjzPOy9.1	
Meeting id- 890 9951 8493 Password- 562591	
11:15 AM	INAUGURATION AND WELCOME ADDRESS BY Conference Chair/Conveners/ Organizing Secretaries
11:45AM-12:00 PM Key Note Speaker	Prof. Padam Singh(Chief Guest)
12:00-12.25 PM IT01	Dr. Neha Singh: - “The Forthcoming of TB Diagnostics: Emergent Technologies and Trends”
12:25-12:50 PM IT02	Dr. Ashok Kumar Mishra: - “Computational Method for Theoretical Research”
12:50-1:15 PM IT03	Dr. S.K Yadav :- “Different Sampling Techniques and Their Uses in Different Areas of Applications”
1.15-1.35 PM IT04	Prof. Pradeep Sharma “Effect of technology on legal education” (KAAF University College Gomoa Fetteh , Kakraba-Kasoa, Ghana (West Africa))
1.35-2.00 PM IT05	Mrs. Usha Mallick “Research in Nursing”

2.30 to 7:30 PM Day 1 (29th May,2024)

Session Chair: Dr.Susheel Kumar Singh

Dr. Roop Kumar

Dr. Shiva Arun

Dr. Hardeep Kour

Dr. Abisarika Bharti

Dr. Shipra Tiwari

Mobile No.- 8299547952

Oral Presentation

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/89099518493?pwd=DWbSm4gSifCgxo0mQxW7ZC0GizPOv9.1>

Meeting id- 890 9951 8493 Password- 562591

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
A1	Dr.Dusu Lalin	A Survey on awareness about anaesthesia and anaesthesiology among the patients undergoing surgery in tertiary care center in Arunachal Pradesh
A2	Dr.ASHWINI KUMAR	Predicting the material properties using DFT based Approach
A3	Dr.Shilpa Premchand Badhe	EXPLORING SHALYATANTRA AS PROMISING AND INOVATIVE SOLUTION IN GERIATRIC ORTHOPEDICS
A4 &A5	Dr.HARI MOHAN SAXENA	Impact of Human Resource Practices on Employee Performance with reference to service industries of Uttar Pradesh
A6	Dr.Sudhakar Prakash	Recent advances in the herbal plant research managing diabetes
A7	Mrs.SOMA RANI KARAN	Impact Green Revolution in india
A8	Dr.Kripa Mani Mishra	High Ionic Conductivity in Sodium Titanate: Na_4TiO_4
A9	Dr.MADHULIKA SINGH SISODIA	A cross-sectional study to know the socio-demographic profile of geriatric population in selected areas of district Hapur.
A10	Dr. Sonal P. Varma	IDENTIFICATION OF ANOPHELIAN MOSQUITOES BLOODMEALS BY USING POLYMERASE CHAIN REACTION (PCR)
A11	Dr.Sneha Jaiswal	Biodegradation studies of Indigo carmine by Bacillus subtilis isolated from dye contaminated soil
A12&A95	Mrs.Swati Seshadri & Miss Padmapriya	STUDY ON THE EFFECTIVENESS AND PERFORMANCE OF UZHAVAR SANTHAI IN CHENGALPATTU DISTRICT
A13	Prof.SHIVSHANKAR TIWARI	Comprehensive Overview of NEET Aspirants' and Passed Students' Experiences, Challenges, and Suggestions for Improvement
A14	Prof.Jagmohan Singh Negi	Synthesis and fungicidal activity of some new Derivatives of N-[4-phenylthiazolyl]-3-Chloro- 4-[3'-iodo-4'-hydroxy-5'-ethoxy]-2'-azetidinones
A15	Mr.Vijay. S	Role of Organic Amendments in Suppression of Soil Borne Pathogens in mulberry
A16	Miss.Rani Kumar Sajane	Insect pests of mulberry and their management in Eastern region of India
A17	Mr.HARISHKUMAR J	Isolation and Characterization of Bioactive Compounds from Morus alba Root: Antimicrobial Efficacy and Toxicological Assessment Using Bombyx mori Model
A18	Dr.KAPIL TYAGI	Optimizing Rice Bran Oil Stabilization and Extraction Methods for Enhanced Nutritional Quality
A19 & A90	Prof.Nikita J. Ambegaonkar & Mr.Kaushal Panchal	Zinc Oxide Synthesis from Fruit peel waste for wastewater treatment
A20	Dr.Monika Gupta	Design of Nanocatalyticsystem from waste derived carbon nanomaterials and its applications in synthesis of heterocycles

A21	Dr.Dr Ritu Mahajan	Callus induction and in vitro shoot formation in Curcuma zedoaria Roscoe
A22	Dr.Nisha Kapoor	Assessment of genetic variants associated with APS3a
A23	Dr.Arati Ghabru	Evaluation of bioactive constituents of Ocimum sanctum
A24	Dr.Sharmin Siddiqui	6.35E+14
A25	Mrs.Nargis Khatun	Evolution of phosphate binders in CKD patients on hemodialysis

**8:00 PM to 11PM Day 1 (29th May,2024) Session Chair: Dr.Seema Tripathi
Dr. Garima Awasthi
Mobile No.- 8299547952**
Oral Presentation
Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/89099518493?pwd=DWbSm4gSifCgxq0mQxW7ZC0GizPOy9.1>
Meeting id- 890 9951 8493 Password- 562591
Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
IT06	Dr. Manisha Shukla	Isolation, Biological Activity and Structure Elucidation of Carbohydrate Containing Moieties
A26	Miss.Aaliya Khan	Evolution of phosphate binders in CKD patients on hemodialysis
A27	Dr.M. Usha Rani	ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND FUTURE OF HEALTH CARE- DOCTORSâ€™™ PERSPECTIVE: AN EXPLORATORY QUALITATIVE STUDY.
A28	Dr.Amal Debnath	Non-timber Forest Products (NTFPs) for food and livelihood security: a case study on local usages and tribal economy in Raima-Surma Valley forest of Tripura, India
A29	Dr.Gajraj Singh	Statistical Analysis of Evaluation of Hearing in Mobile Phone Users
A30	Dr.Sonia Saini	Curcuma longa: A treasurer of health
A31	Dr.Ganapathy, S	Evaluation of Early Maturing Sugarcane Clones for Yield and Quality related traits
A32, A33, A99	Dr.Dhyanadipta Panda, Mrs.Chandralekha Rath & Mr.Ayushman Panda	Impact of Elemental AI in the prevailing HRM
A34	Dr.SHWETA TYAGI	Optimizing Rice Bran Oil Stabilization and Extraction Methods for Enhanced Nutritional Quality
A35	Dr.ANKITA TYAGI	Optimizing Rice Bran Oil Stabilization and Extraction Methods for Enhanced Nutritional Quality
A36	Dr.Seema Rani Sarraf	Coping strategies among smartphone users
A37	Dr.Poonam Singh	Social and Emotional Maturity among Soldiers
A38	Dr.Hema Khanna	Teacher's professional responsibility in relation to administrative styles and organisational climate at secondary level

A39	Mrs.Tushara Modugu	Significance of developing rice varieties resistant to bph
A40	Mrs.Rahinaz Usman Bedrabettu	Tracing the Dual Challenge: Hypoalbuminemia and Low Hemoglobin in Nephrotic Syndrome from Diagnosis to Follow-Up
A41	Miss.Anantpreet Kaur	Isolation of a pure compound using column chromatography and antioxidative potential of Azadirachta indica leaves
A42	Mrs.Shalini singh	A review on Phytoplanktons as bioindicators in river water for ecological assessment
A43	Mrs.A PRAVEENA	Seismic Retrofitting of RCC Exterior Beam-Column Joints Using ECC and AFRP: A Numerical and Experimental Study
A44	Mrs.Unnati Singh	Isolation of Gaddi Sheep Milk Oligosaccharides as Blood Platelet Enhancers
A45	Mrs.Shradha Jaiswal	Mare milk oligosaccharides as anti-oxidant, lipid lowering and post- heparin lipolytic activity.
A46	Miss.Afra khan	Gir Cow Colostrum Oligosaccharides Isolation and Structure Elucidation
A47	Mr.Desh Deepak A P Singh Chauhan	Isolation of Biologically Active Oligosaccharides from Rathi Cow Milk and Their Structure Elucidation by 2D- NMR
A48	Miss.NIKHAT PERVEEN	Safeguarding Child Safety: Understanding the Practices of Child Protection among Government Primary School Teachers in Azamnagar Block, Katihar. Bihar
A49	Mr.NEERAJ SHAILLI SINGH	A STUDY OF PUSH FACTORS THAT IMPACT ATTRITION IN THE HOTEL INDUSTRY
A50	Mrs.C. Lalremtluangi	A review on socio-demographic studies on hypertension

Oral PresentationZoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/86057636274?pwd=duH4kFj0K9ae0gluDNr5wKd54z9nCc.1>

Meeting id- 860 5763 6274 Password- 947929

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
IT07	Dr.Heera Laxmi Jadon	HYDROLYSIS OF ESTER AT DIFFERENT VOLUMES AND TEMPERATURES
A51	Miss.KUMARI AKANKSHA	Stress and the Immune System: Adaptive and Maladaptive Responses
A52	Mr.Rahul Kumar	Understanding the Interplay of Aging and Atherosclerosis
A53	Miss.ASWINI ASOKAN	Fintech Digital Transformation:Nationalised Bank Leading Financial Inclusion
A54	Mr.Pankaj Bisht	ANALYSING CPEC : ITS IMPACT AND SECURITY CHALLENGES FOR INDIA
A55	Miss.Jahnvi Sharma	Prevalence of Vitamin B12 deficiency in Type 2 diabetic patients. A Review
A56	Mr.ANAND RADHESHYAM TIWARI	Sustainable Chromatographic Method for Multi-Component Analysis of Antidepressants: Assessment of greenness with Green Metric Tools
A57	Dr.SREESHYLA HS	Colposcopy in the Diagnosis of Oral Precancer and Cancer – The Current Standing
A58	Mrs.Kiran Sharma	Lived Experiences of Male Inmates: A Pilot Study
A59	Mrs.Fatimah	"Estimation of the Rate of Soil Erosion in the Vlrma basin using RUSLE modelling and Geospatial tool
A60	Miss.Mamta	Role of women in the co-operative dairy movement
A61	Miss.Supreetha L	Effectiveness of Systemic Hydration in Speech-Language Pathologists: A Quasi-experimental Pre-post study
A62	Mrs.Kumari	Morphometric Analysis of Kharkhai River Basin for fluvial erosion susceptibility mapping, Kolhan District, Jharkhand based on Gis Approach.
A63	Mr.Vivek Kumar Bajpai	Synthesis,Structural and Fractal Analysis of Zn Doped BFO Nanostructure
A64	Mr.SANJEEV KUMAR	Larvicidal activity of Parthenium hysterophorus in acetone, methanol and hexane solvents against Mosquito larvae
A65	Mr.Sandesh Paul	Determinants of Antenatal Care Attendance: A Comprehensive Analysis of Influential Factors
A66	Miss.Ragini H R	Predictive Modeling of Land Use Land Cover Dynamics Using Multi-Temporal Satellite Data
A67	Miss.TAHEERA ANSARI	Effectiveness of Alphamethrin and Chlorpyrifos against the larva of Diamondback moth (Plutella xylostella L.)
A68	Miss.Saumya Richa	The Impact of Social Support and Personality Traits on Postpartum Depression
A69	Miss.YAMINI J	PHOTOCATALYTIC ACTIVITY OF BCN/Bi2O3 NANOCOMPOSITES ON TEXTILE DYE EFFLUENT
A70	Mr.Kishanbhai J. Jani	Economic Value Added (EVA) - A key indicator to measure financial performance
A71	Mr.SHAJAAT HUSSAIN AHANGER	HPLC analysis of Curcuminoids and flavonoids in the methanolic rhizome and leaf extracts of Curcuma zedoaria
A72	Mr.Muhammad ismail A T	Synthesis,characterization and application of Chitosan nanoparticles for degradation of organic dyes

A73	Miss.Silpa S Nair	Environmentally Friendly Fabrication and Analysis of Calcium Cross-Linked Carboxymethyl Chitosan Nanoparticles: Application as an Efficient Sorbent for Pb(II) Ion Removal
A74	Mrs.Ahana santha sreedhar	Cellulose bio whiskers for removal of Uranium from industrial waste water
A75	Dr.Bhawana Vijayvergia	Anaemia In Pregnant Women In Area Under Rural Health Training Centre Of Sawai Mansingh Medical College, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India: A Community Based Cross-Sectional Study

6;00 PM to 11PM Day-2 (30th May, 2024) **Session Chair: Dr.Seema Tripathi**
Dr. Abhisarka Bharti
Mobile No.- 8299547952
Oral Presentation
Zoom link: https://us02web.zoom.us/j/86057636274?pwd=duH4kFj0K9ae0gluDNr5wKd54z9nCc.1
Meeting id- 860 5763 6274 Password- 947929
Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
A76	Dr.Deepak Muraleedharan	Internet addiction and its effects on psychological wellbeing among adolescents belonging to urban and rural areas around the city of Jaipur, Rajasthan, India: A cross-sectional study
A77	Dr.Zikra Rahman	Bridging Ayush and contemporary health systems: The imperative for interdisciplinary approach
A78	Miss.Payal Jain	Initiatives to Improve Status of Teachers
A79	Dr.SHARIQ	Accessory great saphenous vein and clinical significance
A80	Mr.Suraj Kumar Chanda	âGHRM Practices in Indian Railways
A81	Miss.Shazia Syed	Diversity of Soil Microflora of Different Plant Species
A82	Miss.Shivangi	Unlocking the Potential of Kombucha: Probiotic Fermented Foods for Gut Health and Beyond
A83	Mr.YASH KUMAR SONKER	METAGENOMICS ANALYSIS OF THE HUMAN GUT MICROBIOME
A84	Mr.ASHUTOSH NANDA	Assessment of eco-friendly sustainable methods for mitigating the charcoal rot disease of sesame in Eastern India, using both in-vitro and in-vivo techniques
A85	Miss.Misbah Arshad	Microbial diversity of different commercial probiotic formulation
A86	Mr.Shivangi Singh	Screening and identification of microbes and responsible enzymes for biodegradation of dyes
A87	Dr.SAI SHANMUKH VEMPARALA	ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND FUTURE OF HEALTH CARE- DOCTORS PERSPECTIVE: AN EXPLORATORY QUALITATIVE STUDY.
A88	Dr.Tejaswini Metta	EXPLORING THE LINK BETWEEN VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY AND UTERINE FIBROIDS: A CASE-CONTROL STUDY
A89	Miss. Rashika Rai	Study of magnetic field on strange quark matters

8:00 AM to 10:00 AM Day-3 (31st May,2024)

Session Chair: Dr.Susheel Kumar Singh

Dr. Alka Singh Bhatt

Mobile No.- 8299547952

Oral Presentation

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/81992105141?pwd=GwQ55ph6UeA31ovrrhwo4VWR9ov15S.1>

Meeting id- 819 9210 5141 Password- 830238

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
A119	Mr.Swapnil Gaur	Role of AI in marketing research
A120	Dr.Dr.Rashmi Bala	Historical Development of Teacher Education: Before and post India
A121	Dr.Sheo Prakash Dwivedi	NEP 2020: Empowering the teacher
A122	Dr.Ritika	Interrelation among physicochemical, thermal, rheological and structural properties of wheat cultivars
A123	Dr.Sushma Sharma	Synthesis Characterisation and Determination of Encapsulation Efficiency of Chitosan Nanoparticles for Ketoconazole
A124	Mrs.Mamta kumari	Weaving dreams on handloom utilizing Manjusha art.
A125	Miss.Aparna sharma	Nanoparticles: new pathway for water remediation
A126	Miss.Mampi Debnath	Determinants of Obesity among the Bengali Adolescents of North Bengal, West Bengal (India)
A127	Mr.SUBHAJIT SARKAR	Comparative Morphometric Analysis of Mahananda River Basins: Pre and Post Channel Avulsion
A128	Dr. Smarajit Maji	Resilience Dynamics in Modeling Buruli Ulcer : A Global Stability Analysis of SEITR-SEI Model with Considerations for Relapse, Immunity Erosion, and Arsenic Contamination in Surface Water
A129	Dr. Seema Tripathi	E-commerce and its Influence on Market Efficiency: An Economic Analysis
A130	Miss.P.VINOTHINI	An Economic Analysis of Area ,Yield and Production of Cotton in India
A131	Miss.ANURADHA PAUL	DIMENSION OF FOOD SECURITY AND MEASURING FOOD SECURITY : A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

2:00 PM to 6:00 PM Day-3 (31st May,2024)

Session Chair: Dr.Susheel Kumar Singh

Dr. Alka Singh Bhatt

Mobile No.- 8299547952

Oral Presentation

Zoom link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/81992105141?pwd=GwQ55ph6UeA31ovrrhwo4VWR9ov15S.1>

Meeting id- 819 9210 5141 Password- 830238

Note: You will get only 10 min for oral Presentation

ABSTRACT ID	SPEAKER	TOPIC
IT08	Dr. Garima Awasthi	Quality Assurance and Quality Control: An Opportunity for Biotechnologists
IT09	Dr.Rajeswari Maddali	Millet Consumption-a plausible approach for achieving food and nutritional security
A91	Miss.elma Khan	Insilico study of phytochemicals of asparagus racemosa and trifolium pratense for anti-cancer potential
A92	Miss.Dave Rushita Bharatbhai	A Review Paper on "Comparative Study of Essential Oil Extraction from Spices and Herbs
A93	Dr.Vandana Dubey	Comparative study of serum interleukin-6 (IL-6), IL-8, & CRP levels in Stable COPD patients & Acute Exacerbation of COPD patients

A94	Miss.Wasima Akhtar	Isolation of beneficial microbes from rice(Joha) rhizosphere
A96	Miss.Kebenle kesen	Isolation and identification of endophytes from the orchid (Cymbidium dayanum)
A97	Miss.Annie	Impact of Childhood Trauma on Emotional Well Being: A Comprehensive Review
A98	Miss.Divyanshi	Unexplained Infertility
A100	Mrs.Shweta Agarwal	A Comparative Study of debate speech analysis using Argumentation Mining in LLMs
A101	Miss.megha agarwal	Sentiment analysis in recognizing emotional tone of text
A102	Dr.Sara Sultana	PHOTOBIMODULATION IN THE TREATMENT OF XEROSTOMIA (DRY MOUTH)- A REVIEW
A103	Dr.Avantika Singh	Unveiling the Taboos: A Systematic Exploration of Menstrual Hygiene Management among Adolescent Girls
A104	Dr.Anandhi Santhosh	A Novel Approach on Predictive Modeling for Banana Crop Yield Optimization-Big Data Analytics
A105	Dr.Rajni Pandey	Climate-Resilient Crop Varieties: Integrating Genetic Modification and Traditional Breeding Techniques
A106	Miss.Mishra Ankita Onkarnath	"Unveiling the Taboos: A Systematic Exploration of Menstrual Hygiene Management among Adolescent Girls"
A107	Mrs.Sadhana Singh	A Comprehensive Literature Review on Employee Engagement: A Rising Concept of Human Resources
A108	Miss.Prashasti Sinha	Nano Revolution: Unveiling the Transformative Potential of Nanotechnology in Advancing Drug Development
A109	Miss.Varsha Maske	Outcome of postpartum intrauterine contraceptive device (PPIUCD) insertion in rural Pune district of Maharashtra, India
A110	Mr.Serumberson Lakhiat	Quantitative Morphometric Analysis of Wah Khri Catchment, West Khasi Hills, Meghalaya
A111	Miss.Roshni Kumari	Nano Revolution: Unveiling the Transformative Potential of Nanotechnology in Advancing Drug Development
A112	Miss.Shakuntla Bharti	Toxic effect of dimethoate(organophosphates) against predatory fish Mystus mystus
A113	Miss. Kritika	Climate-Resilient Crop Varieties: Integrating Genetic Modification and Traditional Breeding Techniques."
A114	Miss.Pruna Srivastava	RNA interference
A115	Miss.Deeksha Shastry	Hemostatic agents used in wound healing
A116	Mr.Nitish Ranjan	Quality Assurance and Quality Control for Analysis of Food and Food products
A117	Dr. Upasana Yadav	Effects Of Heatwaves On Human Health And Its Mitigation
A118	Dr. Pushpendra Singh & Amit Kumar Tripathi	Synthesis and Characterization of some Chalcogen atom bearing Molecules

List of Participated

ID	Name	Role
P1	Prof.PIYALI DE	Participated
P2	Mrs.Kuntal Mandal	Participated
P3	Dr.SURYA JYATI CHAUDHURI	Participated
P4	Dr.Shabnam	Participated
P5	Dr.M. Usha Rani	Participated
P6	Miss.SAKSHI	Participated
P7	Dr.SURYA JYATI CHAUDHURI	Participated
P8	Mr.Kunal	Participated
P9	Dr.Paramjyoti	Participated
P10	Dr.Sheetal Paliwal	Participated
P11	Prof.Susmita Chowdhury	Participated
P12	Dr.ANUPAMA ARYA	Participated
P13	Mr.Kiran N R	Participated

Dr. Neha Singh
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The Forthcoming of TB Diagnostics: Emergent Technologies and Trends

Abstract

Tuberculosis (TB) leftovers a noteworthy universal health challenge, predominantly in low- and middle-income nation state, where timely and precise diagnosis is serious for actual treatment and control. In spite of progressions, existing diagnostic approaches such as culture tests, smear microscopy, and molecular diagnostics expression limitations in sensitivity, specificity, cost, and accessibility. We tried explores the upcoming of TB diagnostics, concentrating on emerging technologies and trends that capacity to revolutionize TB detection. Significant advancements consist of next-generation sequencing (NGS), point-of-care testing, artificial intelligence (AI) applications, innovative biomarkers, biosensors, and progressive imagination procedures. These novelties proposal potential solutions to existing challenges by providing rapid, precise, and reasonably priced diagnostic selections. The addition of these technologies into healthcare systems, exclusively in resource-limited settings, is deliberated, highlighting the essential for capacity building, cost-effectiveness, and reasonable access. By leveraging these emergent diagnostic tools, we can enhance early detection, progress patient outcomes, and make significant strides in the direction of TB elimination.

Key words: Tuberculosis (TB); Diagnostics; Emerging Technologies Trends; Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS); Point-of-Care Testing; Artificial Intelligence (AI); Molecular Diagnostics; Biomarkers

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Computational Methods for Theoretical Research

Abstract:

Quantum chemical Calculations have been an important approach to study the various properties of a molecular system since the advent of feasible approximation method. This approach is an important tool to carry out the theoretical investigations which can be executed through computational techniques having more accuracy, feasibility and less cost. Some popular methods such as *ab-initio* Methods, Semi Empirical Methods, Molecular Mechanics, Molecular Dynamics, Density Functional Theory and Molecular docking can be executed through computational tools which have been discussed in the presentations. These theoretical frame-works have been reported to be competent for calculating physical, chemical and biological properties of a molecular system which enable them to be best fit for the interdisciplinary research.

IT-03

Dr. S. K. YADAV
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School of Physical and Decision sciences,
Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Lucknow
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Different Sampling Techniques and Their Uses in Different Areas of Applications

Abstract

During this presentation, we will explore different methods of sampling, including Simple Random Sampling, Stratified Random Sampling, Systematic Sampling, Cluster Sampling, and Two Stage Sampling. We will discuss how these techniques are applied across various fields. We'll also delve into utilizing additional information and choosing the most suitable sampling method depending on the circumstances. For instance, if the population is uniform for a particular trait, we might opt for Simple Random Sampling or Stratified Random Sampling. Conversely, if the population is diverse concerning the trait being studied, different sampling techniques may be more appropriate.

Keywords: Study Variable, Auxiliary Variables, Bias, MSE, PRE.

2010 AMS Classification: 62D05

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The Psychological impact and coping mechanism of COVID -19 on Staff Nurses'- A retrospective study

Introduction-

The ongoing COVID-19 pandemic has affected people in more than one way. It is accompanied by various morbidity and mortality with long lasting effects, which was impacting public health, with psychosocial consequences across the globe. Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) is an infectious disease caused by a newly discovered coronavirus. Nurses faced lot of difficulties in maintaining the quality of healthcare in those days specially the nurses.

Objectives –

- To assess psychological impact of covid19 in anxiety, depression, stress.
- To assess coping mechanism of the staff nurse .
- To find out the relationship of psychological impact with demographic variables of the staff nurses.
- To find out the relationship of coping mechanism with demographic variables of the staff nurses.

Research Methodology-

Research Design-Descriptive survey research design.

Population of the study- Staff nurses of Govt and Private Hospitals.

Total sample size-300.

Sampling technique- Non probability convenience sampling technique.

Research TOOL- A. Standardized tool (DASS 21 SCALE) was used to measure the depression, anxiety and stress level of the staff nurse due to Covid19.

B. Brief cope scale was used for measuring coping of the staff nurses.

Results-

Staff nurses 51.6% (155) are from the age group of more than 30 years. Staff nurses 50.6% (152) are from the Govt Hospital. Study revealed that 98 (32.67%) staff had moderate level of depression. 121(40.33%) moderate level of anxiety ,103 (34.33%) staff had moderate level of stress and 162 (54%) moderate coping.

Conclusion- The results of the study show that the main psychological impacts of caring for people with COVID-19 manifested by the nurses were anxiety, stress, depressive symptoms.

Key words- Covid-19, Anxiety , Depression , Stress , Coping

Dr. Manisha Shukla,
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Isolation, Biological Activity and Structure Elucidation of Carbohydrate Containing Moieties

Abstract

In the recent scenario the carbohydrate containing moieties like glyco-conjugates, oligosaccharides, glycosides etc. have proven themselves as an important class of compounds which is due to presence of carbohydrate chains in them. Such carbohydrate containing compounds are absorbed in the body easily in comparison to the compounds having no carbohydrates in them. These compounds are being used as antibiotics, antiviral, anti-haemophilic, antioxidant etc. Digoxin is one of the oldest medicines used for cardiac diseases while heparin which also contains carbohydrate is used as anti-coagulant agent. The other examples are erythromycin, roxithromycin, streptomycin, ribabirin etc. are being used as antibiotics and antiviral agents. All these examples contain the monosaccharide units or oligosaccharide chains in them increases its biological activities. Due to presence of carbohydrate chains, its lypophilicity increases and they are absorbed easily in the biological systems and simultaneously increases its response multi-fold in the human body. The presence of carbohydrate chains increases the polarity of such compounds and hence absorption in the body. The highly polar nature of the carbohydrate containing compounds makes it difficult to elucidate its structure. Further, with the advent of sophisticated analytical tools like NMR with recent modulations like 1D and 2D-NMR, it becomes possible to elucidate the stereoscopic structure of any compound and the structures may further be supported by HRMS and ESI-MS mass spectroscopic experiments. In the present paper, we will deal with the recent carbohydrate containing moieties used as medicines, their structures, biological activities along with the process of their isolation, purification and structure elucidation, using recent physicochemical techniques of NMR and mass spectrometry.

Keywords- Carbohydrate, Oligosaccharides, Structure elucidation, 1D and 2D NMR, Mass spectrometry.

Acknowledgement- Authors are thankful to Research and Development grant, Department of Higher Education, UP Government.

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HYDROLYSIS OF ESTER AT DIFFERENT VOLUMES AND TEMPERATURES

ABSTRACT

Esters are intriguing organic compounds that exhibit a distinctive ability to undergo reactions with water, yielding alcohols and either organic or inorganic acids as products. These compounds find their origins in carboxylic acids, with the formation process being referred to as esterification. Hydrolysis is a crucial chemical process, entailing the decomposition of molecules through the cleavage of bonds, resulting in the production of glycerol and fatty acids within an alkaline or acidic environment. Ester hydrolysis involves breaking bonds of ester with water, yielding carboxylic acids and alcohols. This process has many applications such as in the field of pharmaceuticals, plastic industries, and in the fuel industry as biofuels. It produces aromatic compounds in the fragrance industry. Ester hydrolysis also contributes to environmental cleanup by degrading pollutants. This study investigated the hydrolysis of ethyl acetate under varying volumes and temperatures with the same time intervals. Experiments were conducted at three temperatures: 15°C, 25°C, and 35°C, and titrations were performed at six distinct time intervals (0, 10, 20, 30, 40, and 90 minutes) for three different volumes of ethyl acetate (1ml, 2ml, and 3ml). The results demonstrated a clear correlation between ethyl acetate volume and its reaction rate, with larger volumes leading to faster reactions. Furthermore, an increase in temperature positively impacted the reaction rate, resulting in accelerated hydrolysis. The increased volumes of ethyl acetate and higher temperatures were identified as important factors governing the rate of hydrolysis, with larger volumes and elevated temperatures promoting faster reactions. These findings hold significant implications for our understanding of chemical kinetics and have practical applications in industries where precise control of reaction rates is essential.

Keywords: Ester, Hydrolysis, Temperatures, Volume, Reaction kinetics,

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Quality Assurance and Quality Control: An Opportunity for Biotechnologists

Abstract

In the current scenario, it is highly required to make the bridge between the industry and the students of biotechnology. It is a need to guide and prepare industry-ready students. The quality assurance and quality control (QA&QC) sector is also an appropriate place for the biotechnologist. A biotechnologist can cover a wide range of various science and technology divisions including life sciences, chemical, food, pharmaceutical, plant, animal, microbiology, environment, etc. Biotechnologists are involved in the production of various products using these various sciences and technologies. These products are required to get tested based on quality and thus need QA&QC. The current paper suggests various opportunities available in the booming QA&QC sector which is an essential part of every sector. The QA&QC is recognized by the accreditation body National Accreditation Board for Testing and Calibration Laboratories (NABL). NABL is specifically for the accreditation of Testing and Calibration Laboratories (ISO/IEC 17025), and Medical Testing Laboratories (ISO 15189). To work in the QA&QC department biotechnologists, biologists, and chemists have disciplines like biological, chemical, diagnostic radiology QA testing, and forensic. These divisions include various groups such as food and agriculture, drug and pharmaceuticals, air, water, and many more. It is required to provide information, knowledge, and training to the students so that they are acquainted and ready to work in the QA&QC. The students will also be aware of, where and how they can utilize their learning and potential with full zeal.

Keywords- Biotechnology, life science, quality, assurance, industry, microbiology, NABL

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Millet Consumption- a plausible approach for achieving Food and Nutritional security

Abstract

Millets are envisaged as more potent than the other cereals owing to their rich nutrient density and the myriad of physiological functions they execute on the health. Now, in light of existing research, it is evident that millets have immense nutrient potential to curb malnutrition. Exploration of the nutrient potential of millets with particular reference to the resistant starches, carbohydrates, plant proteins, amino acids, vitamins, zinc, calcium and other nutrients under the umbrella of proliferating scientific evidence is the need of the hour. They are considered essential for preventing malnutrition, increasing dietary diversity, and guaranteeing food security on a global scale because of their nutritional makeup, ability to withstand harsh environments, adaptability, and economic advantages.

Keywords: Millet, Resistant starches, Food security, Dietary diversity

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OP-1

Exploring Shalyatantra as Promising and Inovative Solution in Geriatric Orthopedics

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Abstract: To grow older is a natural process. And to have orthopedic problems with growing age is natural thing. There are nearly 12 crore people in India who have crossed the age of 60 years and this figure will increase around 3 % of total population. This population suffers various biological changes and have increased chances of injury, dislocations, joint problems, osteopenia, osteoporosis, rheumatoid arthritis, fractures etc.

Ayurved is Science of Life and believes in prevention rather than cure. Due to current busy and unhealthy life style, we are not able to follow, Dincharya, Ritucharya to stay healthy.

We come across plenty of patients suffering from above mentioned conditions. Here we can think upon vitiated Vatadosha and Asthikshya. Currently there are treatments available as calcium supplements or joint replacement surgeries which are not enough to take total and less expensive care of patients. We have various plants, Rasakalpa and Lifestyle modalities which we can explore as promising and innovative solution in Geriatric Orthopedics.

Keywords: Osteopenia, osteoporosis, Dincharya, Ritucharya, Vatadosha, Asthikshya, Rasakalpa.

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OP-2

Impact of Human Resource Practices on Employee Performance with reference to service industries of Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract: Whether the industry is small or large, human resources management techniques have a significant impact on both employee and organizational performance. The purpose of the current study is to determine how HRM practices affect worker performance in relation to banking sector. A questionnaire was given to 100 workers from service industries of as part of a random sampling technique. Regression analysis and Pearson correlation were used to determine the relationship between HRM practices and employee performance. The findings showed that HRM procedures include hiring and selection, training, pay, performance reviews, and employee involvement improve workers' output.

Keywords: Recruitment, Selection, Compensation, Training, Performance Appraisal, Employee involvement, employee performance.

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OP-3

Recent Advances in the Herbal Plant Research Managing Diabetes

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Abstract: Hyperglycemia, or elevated blood glucose, is a hallmark of diabetes mellitus, a long-term metabolic disease that is often associated with insulin resistance. The use of medicinal plants to treat diabetes is being explored once again. Prototypic compounds found in medicinal plants have been the source of many conventional medications. By using phytoconstituents found in herbal plants, one can manage the factors that lead to the evolution of metabolic disorders and maintain the function of β -cells while restoring blood glucose levels. Anti-diabetic medication research has advanced significantly in recent years, both domestically and internationally. In particular, certain anti-diabetic medications, like SGLT-2 inhibitors and agonists of the glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) receptor, have been shown to protect the kidneys and heart in addition to lowering blood glucose levels. The prevention and treatment of diabetes, as well as its implications, are reviewed in this article, which also serves as a foundation for the creation of novel medications and safe and efficient medical devices.

Keywords: Herbal Plants, antidiabetic activity, vegetables, animal experimentation, antioxidants, pharmacology.

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OP-4

Impacts of Green Revolution in India

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Abstract: The Green Revolution in India was initiated in the 1960s by introducing high-yielding varieties of rice and wheat to increase food production in order to alleviate hunger and poverty. Post-Green Revolution, the production of wheat and rice doubled due to initiatives of the government, but the production of other food crops such as indigenous rice varieties and millets declined. The effects of the green revolution can be studied in two parts, its economic effects and its sociological impact. Two important economic effects of the green revolution are an increase in, and an increase in productivity. The new strategy has widened regional inequalities by limiting the impact of the green revolution to a few States only which were already better off, given that they have dependable sources of water supply for irrigation. The huge cost involved on account of environmental disruption need to be considered in an objective analysis of green revolution.

Keyword: Green Revolution, agricultural production, economic effects, sociological impact, environmental disruption.

High Ionic Conductivity in Sodium Titanate: Na_4TiO_4

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Abstract: Na_4TiO_4 have been prepared using high temperature solid state reaction technique employing Na_2CO_3 and TiO_2 as starting materials. Electrical conductivity (σ) and thermoelectric power (S) of pressed pellet of Na_4TiO_4 have been measured in the temperature range of 440K to the melting point of the material. Results have been reported as $\log\sigma T$ Vs T^{-1} and S Vs T^{-1} plots. It has been observed that σ jumps by a factor of 10 at a particular temperature and reaches the value of the order of 10^{-1} around 1100K. S value show anomaly at the same temperature. This temperature has been referred to as phase transition temperature (T_p) of that solid. The ionic (σ_i) and electronic (σ_e) parts in total conductivity have been evaluated using time dependence study of dc electrical conductivity. It has been observed that contribution of σ_i to σ above T_p is more than 98%, below T_p it decreases but remain close to 94% up to 500K. From these data it has been concluded that the material exists in two phases. The phase above T_p is high ionic phase and below T_p is mixed conductor. In these phase one can expect the existence of Frankel defect and they are probably, the entity of electrical conduction. The enthalpy for the migration of these defects and heat of transport also been evaluated.

Keywords: Electrical transport, phase transition, electrical conductivity, thermoelectric power, heat of transport.

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OP-6

A Cross Sectional Study to know the Socio - Demographic Profile of Geriatric Population in Selected Areas of District Hapur

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Abstract: The health status of the elderly is an important facet of the field of public health.

This is primarily because of increasing old age population and different type of illnesses, especially chronic illnesses. This increase in India's older population and their health status will have impact on their families, communities and the nation.

A community based cross sectional study was carried out in geriatric age group aged 60 years and above in the urban field practice areas of Department of Community Medicine, Saraswathi Institute of Medical Sciences, District- Hapur. The total sample of 580 elderly was selected from 7 localities of Hapur city. All persons were included to be a part of this study after obtaining their consent. The result of study shows that among 580 study subjects, 291(50.2%) were male and 289(49.8%) were female. Majority of elderly were in the age group of 60-69 years (64.5%) in which women exceed men. Mean age of male was slightly higher 69 years as compared to females (67.4) Hindus formed the majority group (74.7%). Three fourth of the elderly lived in joint families (75.2%). Majority of elderly i.e. 51.7% and 24.7% belonged to class IV and III socioeconomic status respectively. Higher proportion of elderly was currently unemployed (65.3%). The literacy status was high among males (73.5%) as compared to females (26.0%). Geriatric care should become an integral part of the primary health care delivery system.

Keywords: Chronic illness, Geriatric, Socio- economic status

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OP-7

Identification of Anopheline Mosquitoes Blood Meals by using Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)

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Abstract: The purpose of this study was to investigate bloodmeal sources of mosquitoes captured from Gondia region, and to identify the probable relation between mosquito species and their food preferences in order to explore scientific information on the vector biology and malaria burden profile and to plan proper strategies for malaria control and eradication.

We have developed a vertebrate specific primer set based on mitochondrial cytochrome b to identify the vertebrate blood host of field collected Anopheline mosquitoes. This investigative assay will be valuable tool for identifying the bloodmeal of field collected mosquitoes where people and alternative mammal hosts are present.

In this survey 4 species of mosquitoes belonging to Anopheles genus have been identified. Among these *Anopheles fluvatils* was the predominant species followed by *Anopheles stephensi*, *Anopheles. culicifacies* and *Anopheles annularies*.

Out of 154 blood meal samples of feeded mosquitoes collected from different habitats 151 samples showed positive reaction while 3 did not show any DNA band with any of the primer tested and hence were considered negative for the blood meal tested.

Keywords: Bloodmeal, Malaria, Anopheles, PCR, Host preference, cytochrome b.

Biodegradation studies of Indigo carmine by *Bacillus subtilis* isolated from dye contaminated soil

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Abstract: Water pollution from the dyeing industry is a major concern because large amounts of colored wastewater are discharged into the water bodies. Vat dyes are widely used for dyeing cotton fabrics. Amongst the vat dyes, indigo dyes are commonly used. Effluents loaded with synthetic dyes are very dangerous because they contain certain chemicals that can be toxic, carcinogenic, or mutagenic to flora and fauna. In addition, it is difficult to degrade the dyes discharged from the textile industry with the processes involving conventional biological treatment. Bioremediation can be a viable alternative to the conventional treatments for the economical and eco-friendly treatment of dye containing wastewater. In the present work, a bacterial strain of *Bacillus subtilis* was isolated from the soil contaminated with dyes from the dying houses located in Nagpur region of India. The biodegradation of Indigo carmine, an azo dye was studied using the isolated bacterium. Decolorization rate was monitored spectrophotometrically and the degraded products were analyzed using GCMS. Various parameters such as pH, temperature, dye concentration, glucose concentration and time were also optimized. The isolated strain of *Bacillus subtilis* was found to decolorize 98.13% of dye (100mg/L) at pH 9 at 30°C within 96 hours under shaking condition. From this it follows that *Bacillus subtilis* can be used to treat wastewater containing azo dyes based on its ability to remove color.

Keywords: Bioremediation, Decolorization, Biodegradation, Indigo carmine, Azo dye, Waste water, *Bacillus subtilis*.

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OP-9

**Comprehensive Overview of NEET Aspirants' and NEET Passed Students' Challenges,
Benefits & Insights**

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Abstract: This research paper aims to provide an in-depth analysis of the experiences, challenges, and suggestions for improvement from both NEET aspirants and those who have successfully passed the examination. By gathering qualitative and quantitative data through surveys and interviews, this paper explores the academic, psychological, and social dimensions of preparing for the NEET exam, highlighting key areas for policy and educational reforms.

OP-10

Synthesis and fungicidal activity of some new Derivatives of N-[4-phenylthiazolyl]-3-Chloro- 4-[3'-iodo-4'-hydroxy-5'-ethoxy]-2'-azetidinones

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Abstract: The present study was conducted to evaluate the fungicidal activity, many phenols and compounds with phenolic groups have antifungal potency. A large number of fungicides are formulated as wettable powders; this is the form most commonly used for spray mixes. They simply inhibit fungus growth temporarily. If the fungus is freed from such substance, it would revive. Such a chemical is called a "fungistat" and the phenomenon of temporarily inhibiting the growth is "fungistasis". Some other chemicals, like certain phenanthrene derivatives and Bordeaux mixture, may inhibit spore production without affecting the growth of vegetative fungistate hyphae. 2-amino 4-Phenyl thiazole is condensed with appropriate ethanol and piperidine aromatic was refluxed on water bath for 1 hr. Various obtaining gave benzal imine and azetidinones respectively and synthesized compounds. Most compounds investigated exhibited significant antifungal activity against *Fusarium solani* to that of Bavistin, the standard used drugs.

Keywords: Azetidinones, antimicrobial activity, 2-amino 4-Phenyl thiazole, EtOH , anhydrous zinc chloride .

**Role of Organic Amendments in Suppression of Soil Borne Pathogens in mulberry
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Abstract: Soil borne diseases are considered as a major threat in crop production and caused by microorganism like fungi, bacteria, virus and nematode. These pathogens survive for longer period in host plants, plant debris and soil which freely moved in soil ecosystem. To control the soil borne diseases, conventional synthetic fungicides are applied at regular intervals throughout the growing period. Regular use of these synthetic fungicides may increase the environmental health concerns and leads to development of resistance to disease causing pathogens. The use of environment friendly approaches such as organic amendments is effective tool to develop the natural suppression of soil borne plant pathogens in soil. The use of organic amendments change the physical, chemical and biological properties as well as soil microbial communities directly or indirectly in the soil and plants. The population buildup of total bacteria, total fungi, siderophores producing bacteria (*Pseudomonas*) and spore forming bacteria (*Bacillus*) due to organic amendment application found to inhibit *Rhizoctonia solani*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Ralstonia sp.* The application of organic amendments changed the composition of the microbial community, modified the relationship among microorganisms in terms of competitiveness or antagonistic, hyperparasitism, induced resistance and decreasing the activity of soil borne pathogens. Organic amendments are found to be effective in suppressing the soil borne pathogens, such as damping off and root rot caused by *Pythium ultimum*, *Fusarium spp.*, *Macrophomina phaseolina* and root knot nematodes. Soil physico-chemical manipulation due to organic amendments supported the antagonistic activity of beneficial microbes. OA also stimulated the germination of fungal resting structures by aldehydes in the absence of its hosts.

Keywords: Organic amendments, Mulberry, Soil Borne, Root rot

Insect pests of Mulberry and their management in Eastern region of India

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Abstract: Mulberry (*Morus* spp.) foliage forms a sole food to silkworms, *Bombyx mori* L. Its quality plays a pivotal role in superior silk fiber production. Like any other plants, mulberry is susceptible to detrimental diseases and infested by insect pests. So far, over 300 insect and non-insect species of pests are known to infest mulberry in varying intensities during different stages of the crop and seasons. In the eastern India 14 species of insects were reported as pests on mulberry, of which three sucking pests, viz., Thrips, Mealy bug and Whitefly have been emerged as major pests due their perennial occurrence, severity, persistent level of abundance and damage potential. The crop is prone to depredation of diverse organisms, because of its fast growth and green foliage throughout the year, in varying proportions either for space, food or both. The pest infestation on mulberry not only reduces quantity, it also hinders the quality by causing a deficiency or physiological disorders which leads to malformed, deformed, chlorotic and nutritionally inferior leaf production. The varied nutritive status of the pest infested mulberry leaves influences the growth and development of silkworms in turn leads to the poor commercial characters of silk. To overcome this problem, efforts may be undertaken to conserve natural enemy complex, as varied coccinellids are present in the mulberry ecosystem of eastern region. Use of pesticides should be very judicious considering the sensitivity of the silkworm to the toxicity of residue of chemicals/ active ingredients. For resistance management especially for whitefly repeated use of same formulation should be avoided and alternatives may be used rotationally. Several botanical oils have been recommended for management of insect pests in mulberry. Moreover, more precise computer based forecasting models may be developed to provide advance warning to the stake holders about the possible outbreak of pests to take protection measures as

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and when required instead of routine spray. It will reduce the cost of production and simultaneously reduce the chemical load to the environment.

Keywords: Mulberry, Insect pests, Eastern India, Coccinellids, Forecasting models.

Isolation and Characterization of Bioactive Compounds from *Morus alba* Root: Antimicrobial Efficacy and Toxicological Assessment Using *Bombyx mori* Model

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Abstract: *Morus alba* Linnaeus, commonly known as the white mulberry, is renowned for its dual significance: it serves as a primary food source for the silkworm, *Bombyx mori*, and it is a rich repository of bioactive compounds with potent medicinal properties. This study focuses on isolating phytochemicals from the mulberry root using ethanol as a solvent. The extraction process yielded 18.56% of phyto-extract containing various compounds, including glycosides, phenols, saponins, terpenoids, tannins, carbohydrates, and flavonoids. The extract was subjected to Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS) analysis, which revealed a diverse array of active and inert secondary metabolites. The crude extract demonstrated significant antibacterial activity, evidenced by a 10 mm zone of inhibition against *Escherichia coli*. In vivo toxicity tests were conducted by administering different concentrations of the extract to silkworm larvae via oral and haemocoel routes. Behavioral and morphological symptoms were monitored to evaluate toxicity. Hemolymph protein profiles of the larvae showed a significant decline in protein band intensity in those treated via the haemocoel route, indicating the toxic nature of the mulberry root extract. However, oral administration did not exhibit similar toxic effects, as reflected in the unaltered hemolymph protein profile and overall larval health. The combined in vitro and in vivo findings of this study underscore the antimicrobial efficacy and dose-dependent toxicity of mulberry root extract. These results pave the way for the isolation and characterization of active biomolecules for potential drug development. Furthermore, the silkworm, *B. mori*, emerges as a viable model system for screening phyto-derivative drugs, highlighting its utility beyond sericulture in biomedical research.

Keywords: *Bombyx mori*, *Morus alba*, Root extract, Soxhlet Extraction, Toxicity.

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OP-14

Optimizing Rice Bran Oil Stabilization and Extraction Methods for Enhanced Nutritional Quality

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Abstract: This review comprehensively explores rice bran oil (RBO), covering extraction, composition, processing, and culinary applications. The study emphasizes RBO's health benefits, focusing on its lipidic fraction with tocopherols, γ -oryzanol, and phytosterols. Extraction methods, including innovative approaches like Two-Step Microwave Assisted Extraction, are detailed. The impact of refining processes on nutritional content is discussed, with a focus on minimizing phytochemical losses. The chemical composition, nutritional profile, and comparative analyses with other cooking oils are analyzed. RBO's potential in biofuel production and its functional properties in culinary applications, such as stability and flavor, are explored. Green extraction technologies and the influence of processing techniques on RBO's nutritional properties are highlighted. Overall, this review provides insights into RBO's diverse applications, nutritional benefits, and potential for sustainable development.

Keywords: Rice bran, Extraction, Fatty Acid, Bioactive, Composition, Nutritional Content, Culinary

**Unveiling the Taboos: A Systematic Exploration of Menstrual Hygiene Management
among Adolescent Girls**

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Abstract: (Van Eijk et al., 2016) Menstrual hygiene management (MHM) profoundly influences adolescent girls' educational and health outcomes in developing countries. Nevertheless, it often goes overlooked and is encumbered by stigma, significantly affecting these young women's opportunities for growth and advancement (Kaur et al., 2018). This systematic literature review dives deep into the prevailing research to uncover the most effective strategies and highlight the enduring challenges in MHM. Key obstacles such as societal stigmas, financial barriers, and a widespread lack of awareness frequently restrict access to essential sanitary resources, aggravating the gaps in education and health (Bhagwat & Jijina, 2020; Chauhan et al., 2018). Yet, there is hope as educational initiatives and community-led interventions are making strides toward enhancing MHM practices and improving these girls' quality of life (Misra et al., 2013; Crofts, 2010). Proper MHM reduces health risks like reproductive and urinary tract infections and curtails school absenteeism, a critical factor in bridging the educational divide and fostering economic parity (Nair et al., 2013; Yamakoshi, 2020). This review emphasizes the need for holistic, culturally attuned approaches that mobilize local communities and harness modern technological and educational innovations to propel MHM progress. By stressing MHM's integral role in achieving Sustainable Development Goals, including health, education, and gender equality, the paper advocates for enhanced policy engagement and improved funding to substantially advance MHM for adolescent girls in underprivileged regions (UNICEF, 2018).

Keywords: Menstrual Hygiene Management, Adolescent Health, Developing Countries, Public Health Policy, Gender Equality, Educational Improvement, Sustainable Development Goals.

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OP-16

A Novel Approach on Predictive Modeling for Banana Crop Yield Optimization-Big Data Analytics

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Abstract: Agriculture plays a vital role in India's economy. Over 58 per cent of the rural households depend on agriculture as their principal means of livelihood. Banana (*Musa spp.*) is one of the world's oldest cultivated fruit plants, originating in Southeast and Indonesia. Banana is also considered the fifth most valuable commercialized agricultural food crop, with a cultivated area of 3.8 million hectares over 122 countries worldwide. India is prominent for producing bananas, contributing approximately 25.7% of the total return and contributes a significant figure to the economy of our Country. Due the impact of climate change in India, most of the agricultural crops are being badly affected in terms of their performance over a period of the last two decades. Predicting the crop yield in advance of its harvest would help the policy makers and farmers for taking appropriate measures for marketing and storage. It involves estimating the yield of crops that will be produced in each area based on various factors such as rainfall and crop management practices by comparing it with previous yield data. In recent years, machine learning has emerged as a powerful tool for predicting crop yields. One of the key advantages of using machine learning algorithms in crop yield prediction is their ability to identify and analyze parameters that affect the yield. The parameters taken for consideration for this study are rainfall, temperature, area and soil fertility. By analyzing these parameters, machine learning algorithms can provide valuable insights that can be used by farmers to choose the right variety of bananas and the optimal time of the year to cultivate. This paper focuses on predicting the yield with a higher degree of accuracy enabling farmers to make informed decisions that can maximize their productivity and profitability.

Keywords: Banana, crop yield, prediction model, machine learning algorithms.

Interrelation among physicochemical, thermal, rheological and structural properties of wheat cultivars

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Abstract: Wheat is the most extensively cultivated cereal crop in the world. The variability in the quality of wheat is mainly due to diversification in sources and environmental variation. It is necessary to access the structural and rheological behaviour of wheat flour with the view to judge their end-product utilization. The presence of different constituents in wheat flour-based food may influence the behaviour of protein or starch during manufacturing because of formation of complexes. Differential scanning calorimetry, pasting analysis, FTIR spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction study, and rheological measurements are used to analyze the functional behavior of wheat flour of different cultivars. The variations in different constituents of flour are responsible for variations in functionality in different food system. The interrelation among the structural, physicochemical, and rheological parameters can be an important tool for characterization of wheat flour. The combined analysis of various techniques would provide the important insight to interrelate the role of different properties on the dough behavior. This study could be advantageous to judge the wheat flour suitability for preparation of wheat flour-based products with desired quality parameters.

Keywords: Wheat, Physicochemical properties, Thermal properties, Pasting properties, Dough rheology

SYNTHESIS, CHARACTERISATION AND DETERMINATION OF LOADING CAPACITY OF CHITOSAN NANOPARTICLES FOR KETOCONAZOLE

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Abstract: Nanoparticles have enormous potential application in drug delivery system. Chitosan nanoparticles have received plenty of attention due to their non-toxicity, biocompatibility, biodegradability and controlled drug release. The objective of the present work was to evaluate the potential of chitosan-tripolyphosphate (TPP) nanoparticles as a carrier in the preparation of Ketoconazole loaded nanoparticles in order to enhance the bioavailability of drug and to reduce dose frequency for preventing the side effects of the drug. Ketoconazole loaded chitosan-TPP nanoparticles were prepared by using Ionotropic gelation method. The cross linking between TPP and chitosan was determined by FTIR studies. The particle size and zeta potential of nanoparticles were studied by dynamic light scattering (DLS) and zeta potential analyser. Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) was used to determine the morphological characteristics of nanoparticles. The variations in the concentration of chitosan and TPP effects the size and zeta potential of particles. The particle ranges from 179 to 196 nm in size and have a positive zeta potential +20 to +18 mV. In addition, the change in the chitosan and drug ratio leads to change in the physicochemical properties of nanoparticles, particle size increases with increase in the concentration of Ketoconazole while the zeta potential decreases. These nanoparticles have good loading capacity of 81% for Ketoconazole. These studies suggest that chitosan can complex TPP to form Ketoconazole loaded nanoparticles and act as a promising system in microbial treatment.

Key Words: Nanoparticles, Chitosan, Ionotropic Gelation, Ketoconazole

OP-19

Callus induction and in vitro shoot formation in *Curcuma zedoaria* Roscoe

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Abstract: *Curcuma zedoaria* Roscoe is an important medicinal plant of pharmaceutical importance. Various *in vitro* approaches can be used for large scale propagation and biodiversity conservation. An efficient micropropagation protocol was developed for long term conservation of this plant species. Shoot buds were used as explants and sterilization using 70% ethanol for 20 sec, HgCl₂ (0.1%) for 3 min and Bavistin (0.4%) for 4 min resulted in 74.0% of uncontaminated explants. The explants were further established on basal MS medium and then transferred to modified MS medium containing different concentrations of BAP and TDZ. MS medium with 2.0 mg/l BAP and 1.5 mg/l TDZ resulted in best shoot multiplication with highest number of shoots per explants. Best *in vitro* root formation was observed in MS medium supplemented with 1.5 mg/l IBA. Callus induction was observed in MS containing different concentrations of 2,4-D and NAA but maximum callus proliferation was observed in MS containing 2.0 mg/l NAA only. Established micropropagated plants showed 83% survival rate on acclimatization to the field conditions. Hence the established protocol could be effectively useful for large scale propagation and conservation of *C. zedoaria*.

Key words: *Curucuma zedoaria*, *in vitro*, callus, growth regulators, biodiversity conservation

Non-timber Forest Products (NTFPs) for food and livelihood security: a case study on local usages and tribal economy in Raima-Surma Valley forest of Tripura, India

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Abstract: Non-timber forest Products (NTFPs) are derived from plants and animals whose tangible values are often made to evade the accomplishment of a country's exchequer. Throughout human history and evolution, forest dwellers have used these products for their daily needs, and nowadays, they are used for income generation. The present study was conducted in Raima Surma Valley Forest (RSVF) of northeast India to understand the importance of NTFPs in the daily life and livelihood security of rural people living in the forest villages in and around this forest ecosystem. This study identified 77 NTFP yielding plants and 20 NTFP-yielding animal species from the survey sites. We recorded globally Endangered (animal species- Hoolock hoolock, *Indotestudo elongata*, and *Manis pentadactyla*), and Vulnerable (*Nilssonia hurum* and *Rusa unicolor*). The whole plant and animals or their parts were used as food, medicine, house construction, ethno-magico-religious activities, and others. Some NTFPs were harvested throughout the year for daily needs, and others were harvested seasonally for consumption and sale (basically in summer). Markets were surveyed to identify the economically significant NTFPs and ascertain their local currency (INR) values to understand their demand around the forest areas. The study revealed that unsustainable harvesting of NTFPs from RSVF is the primary cause of species decline. Therefore, illegal and unsustainable ways of harvesting of NTFPs should be restricted. Sustainable harvesting of the economic importance of NTFPs under government supervision is recommended. Thus, it can save this important forest (watershed) for future long-term poverty drop for the rural peoples of this zone and manage the forest for ecotourism and water conservation.

Keywords: Non-timber forest product (NTFP), Tripura, IUCN red list, Diversity, Rural livelihoods, Forest village

OP-21

Statistical Analysis of Evaluation of Hearing in Mobile Phone Users

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Abstract: In today's world, mobile phones have become an essential component. Despite their many daily advantages, mobile phones can have negative consequences on a person's health. The ear, which is the organ closest to a phone, is most affected by the electromagnetic waves that are produced by them. Hearing loss that is irreversible may arise from prolonged exposure to these waves and noises. Therefore, the goal of the current study was to evaluate the relationship between the amounts of time spent using a mobile device and hearing loss. In the ENT Department at Rajindra Hospital in Patiala, a cross-sectional study of mobile phone users aged 20 to 40 was carried out over the course of six months, from August 1, 2022, to January 31, 2023. Three groups of 600 volunteers were selected based on how long they had been using their phones. DPOAE and pure tone audiometry were employed to evaluate the subjects' hearing impairment. All three groups showed varying degrees of hearing loss on PTA and DPOAE, and there was a significant correlation between hearing loss and the amount of time spent using a mobile phone. The group that used a mobile phone for more than an hour a day for at least four years had a higher proportion of sensorineural hearing loss than the control group ($p=0.001$), which was statistically significant. Long-term mobile phone users are more likely to experience hearing loss, particularly in their dominant ear.

Key Words: DPOAE, Electromagnetic waves, Mobile phones, PTA, Sensorineural hearing loss

OP-22

Evaluation of Early Maturing Sugarcane Clones for Yield and Quality related traits

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Abstract: Development of varieties in for different maturity groups is of paramount importance in sugarcane cultivation to realize higher recoveries in sugar mills. The early maturing sugarcane varieties are chosen in the beginning of crushing season for higher sugar recoveries and yield. The present field experiments were carried out to assess the performance of early maturing sugarcane clones for cane yield, quality and its contributing traits at sugarcane Research Station (TNAU) Cuddalore, Tamil Nadu, India. Data were recorded for germination per cent, number of tillers (x1000/ha), stalk length (cm), stalk diameter (cm), single cane weight (kg), cane yield (t/ha) Brix %, sucrose %, Purity %, CCS % and sugar yield (t/ha). Overall performance in the Initial Varietal Trial, the early maturing clone CoA 12322 was found to be better for cane yield (130.52 t/ha) and CCS yield (16.75). Another clone CoV 12356 was found to be better for quality traits viz., brix (21.75%), sucrose (17.82 %) CCS (12.75%) and purity (90.63%) over the check variety CoA 92081. From the Advanced Varietal Trial, early maturing clone, CoC 11336 was found to be better for cane yield (132.56 t/ha) and its contributing traits like number of millable canes (125.33x1000 /ha), Stalk length (294.75 cm), stalk diameter and single cane weight (1.55 kg) over the check CoA 92081. The same clone CoC 11336 was found to be better for CCS yield (16.75 t/ha) and its contributing traits viz., brix %, sucrose % and CCS % over best standar CoC 01061. Hence, these three early clones could be forwarded for the confirmation of the results for better cane and sugar yield under multi-location trials for release as a new sugarcane variety.

OP-23

Impact of Elemental AI in the prevailing HRM

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Abstract: The integration of intelligent systems has profoundly impacted decision-making processes that were previously complex tasks for humans. Human resource professionals are vital in improving the quality of business and investment decisions. Thus, it is essential to consider the use of artificial intelligence (AI) to address fundamental business challenges and revolutionize methodologies, showcasing AI's potential. AI enhances the precision and efficiency of various human resource management processes, surpassing traditional human abilities. This article aims to assess the strengths and limitations of this emerging technology in reshaping HR management. Additionally, it seeks to find ways to harmonize human and computer efforts. In the constantly evolving landscape of business and human resource management, exploring how AI can address current HR and business challenges is crucial. AI can streamline recruitment by automating candidate screening, thereby saving time and reducing human error. In performance management, AI can provide real-time analytics and feedback, helping managers make informed decisions. Moreover, AI-driven tools can assist in employee engagement by predicting turnover risks and suggesting retention strategies. Furthermore, the article focuses on enhancing the skills of human resource managers, empowering them in key business areas such as planning, organizing, staffing, directing, coordinating, controlling, and decision-making. AI can augment HR managers' capabilities by providing data-driven insights and automating routine tasks, allowing them to concentrate on strategic initiatives.

Ultimately, the article underscores the transformation of human resource management through AI, highlighting its potential to make more impactful and beneficial decisions for society. This powerful integration fosters organizational development and adherence to societal principles,

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ensuring that businesses can adapt to the changing landscape while maintaining a human-centric approach. By embracing AI, HR professionals can enhance their decision-making capabilities and contribute to more efficient and effective business operations.

Keywords- Artificial Intelligence, Human Resource Management, organization, transformation, Precision and efficiency.

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Significance of developing rice varieties resistant to Brown planthopper

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Abstract: The brown planthopper (BPH, *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål) is the most destructive rice pest, causing yield losses ranging from 20% to 80% and resulting in an estimated annual economic loss of approximately \$300 million in Asia. Biotypes 1 and 2 are predominantly found in East and Southeast Asia, while biotype 3 was developed in the laboratory by rearing insects on a resistant variety. The most destructive biotype in South Asia, particularly in the Indian subcontinent, is biotype 4. Over time, new virulent biotypes may evolve that can overcome the existing resistance genes. BPH causes severe damage to rice crops by sucking sap from the xylem and phloem tissues, ultimately leading to 'hopper burn.' Additionally, BPH indirectly harms crops by transmitting viral diseases such as grassy stunt virus and ragged stunt virus. Currently, the primary method for controlling BPH populations is the application of chemical pesticides like imidacloprid, which is costly and poses risks to health and the environment. These pesticides kill natural predators and eventually lead to insecticide-resistant BPH biotypes. Therefore, developing host-plant resistance is the most economical, effective, and environmentally friendly approach to managing BPH and increasing rice yields. Approximately 37 BPH resistance genes have been identified in indica and African rice varieties, as well as in wild germplasms such as *Oryza officinalis*, *O. minuta*, *O. nivara*, *O. punctata*, *O. rufipogon*, and *O. latifolia*. Various genes/QTLs associated with BPH resistance including *Bph1*, *bph2/BPH26*, *Bph3*, *Bph6*, *bph7*, *BPH9*, *Bph12*, *Bph14*, *Bph15*, *Bph17*, *BPH18*, *bph19*, *Bph20*, *Bph21(t)*, *Bph27*, *Bph27(t)*, *Bph28(t)*, *BPH29*, *QBph3*, *QBph4*, *QBph4.2*, *Bph30*, *Bph32*, *Bph33*, *Bph35*, and *Bph36* have been fine-mapped by researchers worldwide. The identification of these genes has intensified marker-assisted breeding and the pyramiding of these genes into elite susceptible cultivars, aiming to achieve durable resistance against BPH.

Key word: Brown planthopper, rice, biotypes, marker assisted breeding

"Climate-Resilient Crop Varieties: Integrating Genetic Modification and Traditional Breeding Techniques."

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Abstract: This research paper investigates the development of climate-resilient crop varieties through the integration of genetic modification and traditional breeding techniques. It addresses the research question of how these integrated approaches can contribute to the resilience of crops in the face of climate change. The study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining a systematic literature review with empirical research, including field trials and interviews.

Key findings indicate that the integration of genetic modification and traditional breeding techniques can significantly enhance climate-resilient traits, such as drought tolerance, pest resistance, and salinity tolerance, across multiple crop species. These findings support the hypothesis that integrated techniques offer a promising pathway to improve crop resilience.

Implications of the research highlight the scalability and applicability of integrated techniques, the potential environmental and socioeconomic benefits, and the need for addressing regulatory complexities and public perceptions. Stakeholders, including policymakers, businesses, and farmers, are urged to collaborate and implement recommendations to support the development and adoption of climate-resilient crop varieties.

Keywords: Climate-resilient crops, Genetic modification, Traditional breeding, Crop resilience, Climate change, Agriculture, Integrated techniques, Sustainability, Food security, Policy recommendations.

Isolation of pure compound using column chromatography and antioxidative potential of Azadirachta Indica leaves

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Abstract: *Azadirachta indica* or neem has a long history of use in traditional medicine due to its wide range of pharmacological characteristics. In this study, we investigated the chemical composition of neem leaves along with their antioxidative potential. This is the first report on the isolation of pure compound from neem leaves using silica gel column chromatography. Methanolic extraction of the leaves was followed by column chromatographic separation. Acetophenone was identified as the primary compound in the isolated fraction by gas chromatography and mass spectrometry analysis (GC-MS). The antioxidant activity of the methanol extract of leaves was assessed by 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) assay. The results showed an IC₅₀ value of 32.963 µg/mL indicating the extract's effectiveness in scavenging free radicals. Furthermore, the extract's total phenolic content was quantified using the Folin-Ciocalteu method, yielding a value of 3.067 mg Gallic acid equivalents (GAE/g extract) highlighting the abundance of phenolic compounds with antioxidant properties. The identification of acetophenone aligns with previous research on its presence in pesticidal neem oil as well as its roles in fragrance, flavor enhancement, and industrial applications. Overall, this study not only advances the understanding of neem leaves as a source of natural antioxidants but also demonstrates the efficacy of silica gel column chromatography in isolating bioactive compounds from crude extracts. The findings provide a foundation for future investigations into the versatile potential of acetophenone and its applications in various industries including beverages, fragrances, and food additives.

Keywords: antioxidant, DPPH, GC-MS analysis, column chromatography, acetophenone.

A Review on Phytoplankton as Bio indicators in River Water for Ecological Assessment

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Abstract: Phytoplanktons, a diverse group of microscopic algae living in aquatic environments, serve as a crucial role in aquatic ecosystems as primary producers and bioindicators or ecological indicators of environmental health due to their sensitivity to environmental changes. This review paper is a summary of several studies on phytoplanktons as bioindicators in river water systems. The purpose of writing to this review paper is the summarization of the some previous research on phytoplanktons as bioindicator in fresh water river systems. Bioindicators are organisms or biological systems used to assess the health of an environment, reflecting changes in ecological conditions. Ecological assessment employs bio indicators to evaluate the health and quality of ecosystems. This paper also examines the use of phytoplankton as bioindicators for assessing river water quality and ecological integrity. This discussion explores the significance of phytoplankton in assessing water quality and detecting pollution events. Drawing upon a synthesis of literature and case studies, the paper explores phytoplankton diversity, responses to environmental stressors, monitoring methods, case studies, challenges, future directions, and recommendations for effective ecological assessment.

Keywords: Phytoplanktons, Water Quality, Bioindicators, Ecological Assessment, Physicochemical parameters, DO, BOD etc.

Seismic Retrofitting of RCC Exterior Beam-Column Joints Using ECC and AFRP: A Numerical and Experimental Study

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Abstract : To prevent structural damage from seismic activity, it is crucial to retrofit the structural elements promptly. Beam-column joints are particularly susceptible to damage as they bear the forces from adjacent beams and columns. The specimens were subjected to reverse cyclic loading to assess This paper proposes a method for upgrading RCC exterior beam-column joints with exterior attached Engineered Cementitious Composites (ECC) and Aramid Fiber Reinforced Polymer (AFRP) sheet at 45° orientation. their strength, ductility, energy absorption, and stiffness degradation. The goal of this work is to use the ABAQUS/CAE (6.14) software to construct a three-dimensional numerical model. The concrete damage plasticity (CDP) model was used to determine the nonlinear properties of concrete by analysing the reaction of the structure. The findings indicate that better performance is provided with NSM retrofitted specimens with a 45-degree orientation demonstrated significant improvements in all the properties. The mean variance between the results of the experimental testing and the finite element analysis was less than 10%.

Keywords: Beam-column joints, Retrofitting, NSM-Strengthening, Engineered Cementitious Composites, AFRP Sheet, Cyclic Loading

Isolation of Biologically Active Oligosaccharides from Rathi Cow Milk and Their Structure Elucidation by 2D- NMR

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Abstract: Biological importance of cow milk is well defined in Indian medicinal system of Ayurveda and Charak Samhita. It has brain developing, bone developing, strength rejuvenating properties. In recent researches it was postulated that the biological activity of any milk is due to its carbohydrate contents which are present there as oligosaccharide chains. These oligosaccharides are made up of glucose, galactose, GlcNHAc, GalNHAc, Fucose and Neuraminic acid, linked together with O-glycosidic linkages with α or β glycosidic linkages at various positions of monosaccharides present there in constituting novel and rare oligosaccharides. During our recent investigations on cow milk oligosaccharides of various cow species available in India, we have concentrated on the cows residing in Rajasthan state of India where the weather is arid and dry, resulting in the change of nature of milk oligosaccharide present in the cow's milk of Rajasthan. We have investigated Kankrej, Tharparkar and Rathi species of cow of Rajasthan origin. We find in most of the cases that the oligosaccharides present in the milk of above discussed cows milk were not present as free or reducing oligosaccharides rather they were present as their methyl glycosides changing their behavior and biological activities. In the present study, we have collected the Rathi cow milk from Panchmukhi district of Rajasthan state. The milk was collected in bulk i.e. 10 liters and processed by modified method of Kobata and Ginsburg for obtaining the crude oligosaccharide mixture which was further acetylated by pyridine and acetic anhydride for obtaining their acetylated derivative. It was then purified further by Thin layer chromatography and column chromatography for obtaining their acetylated oligosaccharide in their purest form. It was then investigated by recent physicochemical techniques of NMR (¹H, ¹³C, COSY, TOCSY, HSQC, and HMBC) experiments along with Mass spectrometry. This Paper will deal in details with the structure elucidation of a novel Hexasaccharide. The name of the oligosaccharide has been named as Rathose which is originated from the species of the animal i.e. Rathi cow.

Keywords: Cow Milk Oligosaccharides, Structure Elucidation, 2D NMR, Mass Spectrometry, Isolation & Purification

Safeguarding Child Safety: Understanding the Practices of Child Protection among Government Primary School Teachers in Azamnagar Block, Katihar. Bihar

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Abstract: “I’m a teacher. A teacher is someone who leads. There is no magic here. I do not walk on water. I do not part the sea. But I just love children.”¹-**Marva Collins**

5th September 2023 The Hindu published an article entitled “Primary, middle schools in Bihar’s Katihar struggle sans basic amenities”² is an eye opener in many aspects. Ideally Teachers have a critical role in shielding children's rights and their protection. Teachers can make a significant and positive impact on the lives of children throughout their contact with the children formally and informally. Teacher’s consciousness of child protection is momentous in this context. In this setting the present study has undertaken with an observation to find out the child protection responsiveness, among primary school teachers in Azamnagar Block in katihar district.

This paper explores the understanding and practices of child Protection among primary school teachers in the Azamnagar Block of Katihar, Bihar. The study aims to evaluate teachers’ responsiveness of child protection, their capability to identify signs of abuse or neglect, and their awareness with reporting procedures. Furthermore, it tests the challenges teachers face in implementing child protection concern and their approaches for maintaining a safe secure and environment for students.

¹ <https://quotesmasala.medium.com/62-quotes-about-teacher-student-relationship-inspirational-quotes-d2fc91a3553a>

² <https://www.thehindu.com/news/national/other-states/primary-middle-schools-in-bihars-katihar-struggle-sans-basic-amenities/article67272383.ece>

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Through interviews organized and completed with primary school teachers (Exclusive Government Primary School) of Azamnagar block, the research inquires the extent of training received by teachers on child protection and their basic understandings of its importance in the school setting. It investigates teachers' understanding of child protection and their role in child protection overall.

Findings allocate that while few teachers have received training on child protection which is limited and somehow clueless for them, there are gaps in their understanding and practices. The study indicates the need for ongoing training and support for teachers to enhance their capacity to protect children effectively. It highlights the importance of creating a safe and inclusive school ambience where children feel calm and comfortable.

Overall, this study will be a valuable source for multistakeholders like policy makers, civil society, and specialists in related fields of child protection, mainly Education and Child Protection.

Keywords: Child protection, Government Primary School, Primary Teachers, Awareness, Challenges, Azamnagar, Katihar, and Safe Environment.

A Study of Push Factors that Impact Attrition in the Hotel Industry

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Abstract: Hotel Industry is the fastest-growing Industry in the World. It has contributed US\$ 40 Billion to the GDP of India in the year 2022 and by 2027 it will contribute US\$ 60 Billion in the year 2027 according to Hotel Association of India (HAI) and Benori Knowledge research 'Vision 2047. It is indicated that it would be near to 1\$ Trillion by 2047.

The hotel industry experiences high attrition rates due to certain push factors which majorly include -

The lack of a healthy working environment and long working hours in comparison to the low wages lead to unsatisfactory thoughts in the minds of the employees leading them to question the low career progression made by them.

To emphasize the hospitality sector, the employees have to ensure to appear in a hospitable manner, even though they are not willing to because it will impact customer satisfaction, therefore the emotional labour caused by the constant suppression of emotions can lead to job dissatisfaction which is a major reason for the arising of the intention to quit.

The hospitality industry builds up high levels of stress in employees who want to manage their work and at the same time get involved in family and other personal activities. This is another key factor that erodes the work-life balance, reducing the level of devotion of employees towards their jobs and further leading to the loss of interest in the job these are the few causes that create the intention to quit and soon after this intention leads to attrition.

Keywords: Hotel, Industry, Push Factors, Attrition, Employee

Stress and the Immune System: Adaptive and Maladaptive Responses

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Abstract: Stress is a crucial adaptive reaction that helps organisms overcome challenges and maintain equilibrium. Immune cells have a crucial function in regulating responses to various stresses. Therefore, stress's impact on immunity should differ depending on the stressor. Epidemiologically, stress may cause inflammation or immunological suppression. However, without a conceptual context, these effects might look chaotic and confusing. The authors have explored the involvement of stressor diversity in the neuroimmune axis. Stress may cause a variety of immunological consequences by altering brain rhythms and sending neuronal and endocrine mediators to the periphery. Understanding immunological responses to stressors is crucial for understanding the role of stress in clinical diseases, modulating it, and using adaptive stress responses as therapeutic potential.

Keywords: Brain, Homeostasis, Immunity, Inflammation, Stressor

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OP-33

UNDERSTANDING THE INTERPLAY OF AGING AND ATHEROSCLEROSIS

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Abstract: One of the main causes of cardiovascular illness and death, atherosclerosis presents a serious threat to public health, especially in aging populations. Atherosclerotic plaques develop due to a combination of conventional risk factors such as smoking and hypertension, as well as age-related vascular changes. The extracellular matrix changes and inflammatory cell deposition that characterize the pathophysiology of advanced atherosclerotic plaques highlight the intricacy of the disease's course and the possibility of plaque rupture. Aging of the arteries causes arterial remodeling and stiffness that exacerbates the atherosclerotic process. The present review work emphasizes arterial aging leading to atherosclerosis and age-related cardiovascular disorders. The correlation between the aging process and atherogenesis underlines the need for focused therapies to maintain arterial elasticity and lower inflammation to reduce the risk of cardiovascular diseases.

Keywords: Aging; Atherosclerosis; Cardiovascular diseases; Inflammation; Stiffness.

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OP-34

**FINTECH DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION: NATIONALISED BANK LEADING
FINANCIAL INCLUSION**

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Abstract: Nationalized banks are crucial to financial inclusion, especially in countries like India. Collaboratively, nationalised banks and fintech companies can maximise the benefits of digitalization for financial inclusion. Nationalised banks provide vast networks, regulatory expertise, reputation, and trust, whereas fintech startups bring technological know-how, creativity, agility, and a customer-focused approach. When combined, they may provide comprehensive solutions that successfully close the gap in financial inclusion and meet the demands of various clientele. The combination of fintech and nationalised banks in their embrace of digitalization is driving greater financial inclusion and transforming the banking industry. Mean and Standard deviation has been used for the analysis of data. Chi-Square test has been conducted for the test of hypothesis. In this study dependent, controlling and Independent variable were identified and a model has been created for the research. Through collaborations, technology, and government support, they might create new channels for servicing the under banked and unbanked masses, ultimately fostering inclusive economic growth and development. Analysing the socio-economic effects of nationalised banks' fintech activities and the effectiveness of financial inclusion measures is critical as the economy transitions to a fully digitalized future. According to a poll conducted among 150 clients (which includes 80 female and 70 male respondents) of different nationalised banks (SBI,PNB,BOB,IOB and Union Bank), an individual's socioeconomic circumstances have a big impact on their banking preferences. It was found that the banking business is significantly revived by financial technology. The nationalised bank accelerates the path of financial inclusion. Adding to the body of knowledge on fintech and financial inclusion, this study provides nationalised banks with a knowledge base on which to concentrate future advancements. In recent years, we have seen an increase in the number of account users in India, but these accounts are still dormant. Rural India is still lagging behind full-fledged financial

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inclusion even after the introduction of fintech in the banking sector. More effort and strategies have to be brought in for inclusive financial inclusion. Comprehensive financial inclusion may be achieved through continuing cooperation between nationalized banks and fintech companies, even in the face of obstacles like the digital divide and regulatory compliance. Keywords: Fintech, Nationalised banks, Digitalisation, Financial inclusion

ANALYSING CPEC : ITS IMPACT AND SECURITY CHALLENGES FOR INDIA

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Abstract

The Pakistan- China relations have always had India as its central theme; with China trying to balance India in South Asia while Pakistan seeing China as a counter weight to India. CPEC is passing through Gilgit- Baltistan (GB) region which is a disputed area and illegally occupied by the Pakistan. Gilgit- Baltistan connects both Pakistan and China through Karakorum Highway. Pakistan, unlike India, has not produced an accession instrument. Endorsing the CPEC without consulting India will have security implications to India's territorial sovereignty. The corridor will lead to further integration of northern areas into Pakistan and may enable their occupation. Even Chinese presence may become a permanent feature, creating a possibility of future claims by Chinese for the strategically important areas of Gilgit - Baltistan. Since, the Partition of India in 1947 Pakistan's state authorities and local government bodies along with the army has controlled the territory to various extents. The increasing Sino-Pak Defence nexus, nuclear and missile technologies and strategic contacts are a cause of concern for India. The South Asian powerhouse is edged by two of its rivals from the past, both of which it has engaged in conflict with and is therefore in a precarious situation. Issues that encompass India's territorial integrity significantly challenge its strategic and geopolitical interests in the region. India is opposed to the proposal of the CPEC and thus, must work out own stratagem that would assist as a counter-weight in the region. The China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) involves Gilgit-Baltistan and this study will investigate the geo-economics and geo-politics of CPEC and security challenges of this corridor for India's national security.

Keyword: CPEC, India, China, Pakistan, Gilgit- Baltistan, Economic, Security

Prevalence of Vitamin B12 deficiency in Type 2 diabetic patients. A Review

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Abstract: Vitamin B₁₂ also named as Cobalamin, is a water-soluble vitamin. It acts fundamental role in Neurological function, Optimal Haemopoiesis and DNA Synthesis. The deficiency of Vitamin B₁₂ features as the haematological and neuro cognitive dysfunction. Diabetic patients have been demonstrated highly prevalent of Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency. The purpose of the current study to review the literature related to the prevalence of Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency in type 2 diabetic patients. The studies assess that the prevalence of Vitamin B₁₂ deficiency is ranges about 5.8 to 52% in diabetic patients. Such as the study of D. Malla et al reported as high as 50.95% prevalence of Vitamin B12 deficiency in diabetic patients. However, the patients enrolled in the study are on metformin treatment. Several Studies reported that the deficiency of Vitamin B₁₂ may associated with the treatment of Metformin and old age population. Metformin is known as the initial hypoglycaemic drug to treat Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. It prescribed by many health practitioners as front-line treatment for T₂DM. It is used as monotherapy or combined with other drugs according to the need with some of the mild or self-limiting side effect of the drug. However, studies reported that the prevalence of vitamin B₁₂ deficiency is highly associated with dose and duration of metformin treatment in diabetic patients. Old age population may associate due to the low absorption capacity of the micronutrient in that period of lifecycle. The deficiency of vitamin B₁₂ leads to various complication related to peripheral neuropathy which diagnose as diabetic neuropathy. The literature indicates the necessity of screening status of serum Vitamin B12 in patient of diabetes regularly will help to be aware.

Keywords: Vitamin B12, Diabetes Mellitus, Metformin, Old Age, Diabetic Neuropathy

OP-37

**Sustainable Chromatographic Method for Multi-Component Analysis of Antidepressants:
Assessment of greenness with Green Metric Tools**

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Abstract

The terms "green chemistry," refer to approaches that minimize the use of feedstock's, reagents, energy, and waste in the chemical industry to protect the environment and conserve resources.

A new, rapid, reliable, and eco-friendly liquid chromatographic method was optimized and validated for the determination of Fluoxetine HCL and Olanzapine in pharmaceutical drugs and drug products. The separation of the active analytes was achieved using an isocratic mode of reverse-phase liquid chromatography with a diode array detector using wavelength 227nm. The mobile phase consisted of a mixture of phosphate buffer, acetonitrile, and ethanol in the ratio of 40:40:20 (v/v/v). A L1 column (150 x 4.6mm, 5 μ m) was used, with a flow rate of 1.5mL/min and an injection volume of 5 μ L. The temperature of column oven and the auto-sampler was maintained at 45°C and 25°C respectively. The developed method was validated as per ICH and observed that the method is specific, précised, robust with slight change in flow of mobile phase, column temperature and pH of buffer solution. The method found linear from 50-150 μ g/mL for olanzapine and 203-610 μ g/mL for Fluoxetine, and accuracy was assessed separately for tablets and capsules by performing recovery tests. For tablets, recovery was tested in the range of 52-157 μ g/mL for olanzapine and 204-606 μ g/mL for fluoxetine HCl. For capsules, the recovery range was 49-150 μ g/mL for olanzapine and 209-605 μ g/mL for fluoxetine HCl. The greenness of the proposed methods was evaluated using various well-established green assessment tools, such as the Analytical Eco-Scale, NEMI, GAPI, and AGREE. The newly developed and validated eco-friendly method was applied for the estimation of active pharmaceutical ingredients, tablet dosage forms and it was found to be suitable for the determination of Fluoxetine HCL and Olanzapine.

Keywords: Eco-friendly chromatographic method; Green HPLC method; Validation; Simultaneous assay; Green metric tools; RP-HPLC.

OP-38

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Colposcopy in the Diagnosis of Oral Precancer and Cancer – The Current Standing

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Abstract: Oral cancer is the 6th most common cancer in the world, associated with high mortality and morbidity. It is also associated with poor prognosis. But, the prognosis is relatively good if it is diagnosed in early stage. Being associated with premalignant stage, oral cancer offers the advantage of diagnosing it in its early stage. There are numerous diagnostic aids available for diagnosing oral precancer and cancer in early stage. These adjuncts include vital tissue staining, conventional cytology, brush biopsy, liquid cytology, optical techniques such as spectroscopies, vizilite, VELscope, special stains, enzyme histochemistry, molecular methods ect. Colposcopy is the direct microscopic procedure that is routinely used in the diagnosis of cervical pathologies including cervical cancers. Currently, few researches have tried its usage in diagnosing oral lesions including oral precancer and cancer. This presentation provides an overview on the current standing and usage of colposcopy in diagnosing oral precancer and cancer.

OP-39

**Proceeding of 3rd Online International Conference on Advance Interdisciplinary Research
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A Comprehensive Literature Review on Employee Engagement: A Rising Concept of Human Resources

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Abstract: In today's business scenario every organization is focusing on the job satisfaction of the employees but now business organizations emphasize employee engagement, a rising concept in human resource management. Job satisfaction and employee engagement are used interchangeably but employee engagement has a broader perspective in business organization employee engagement is the commitment of the workforce toward the organization's vision and goals. The degree of interest and connection that employee feels in their work is known as employee engagement. Several factors, including the character of leadership and the sense of belonging in the workplace, influence employee engagement. A crucial element to engaging employees to achieve organizational objectives and goals is to find out the factors influencing employee engagement. The study focuses on the key drivers of employee engagement and how it can be measured. This article reviews select literature on factors influencing employee engagement and how it can be measured. The selection of papers was done through various database sites which mentioned the observations and summarized them after review of various previous research papers.

Keywords: employee engagement, job satisfaction, human resources, measurement of employee engagement.

OP-40

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**Unveiling the Transformative Potential of Nanotechnology in Advancing
Drug Development**

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Abstract: Nanotechnology delves into the exploration of minute structures ranging from 0.1 to 100nm. It stands as a specialized field poised to revolutionize the landscape of the pharmaceutical industry in the foreseeable future. This interdisciplinary domain intersects with diverse fields including biophysics, molecular biology, biotechnology, and different branches of medicine. Pharmaceuticals is actively engaged in the innovation of novel drug delivery systems aimed at overcoming the limitations inherent in conventional approaches. This endeavor holds promise for enhancing therapeutic efficacy and patient outcomes in the realm of pharmaceuticals.

Keywords: Drug discovery, Nanomedicine, Nanotechnology, Viral Disease

OP-41

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Outcome of postpartum intrauterine contraceptive device (PPIUCD) insertion in rural Pune district of Maharashtra, India

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Abstract

Background: The unmet need for family planning in India is 65 % in the first year of the postpartum period, but only 26% of women are using any form of contraceptive. A large proportion of women in the postpartum period want to avoid the next pregnancy and wish to accept contraception to space or limit their future pregnancies.

Objective: We aimed to determine the outcome of PPIUCD insertion in terms of continuation, discontinuation and safety 6 weeks after initiation among the user women.

Method: This is a community-based prospective cohort study conducted with a sample size of 200 women in rural Haveli and Junnar blocks of the Pune district. The public health facilities where the maximum number of deliveries conducted were selected. Women in the age group 18 - 49 years to whom IUCD was inserted immediately after their delivery (are PPIUCD users) were included in the study from these facilities. A pretested semi-structured questionnaire was administered at enrolment and at 6 weeks to determine the outcome and safety of PPIUCD.

Results: From the total of 200 women sampled for the study 199 (99.50 %) participants completed the 6th week follow up study questionnaire. The proportion of continuation and discontinuation of PPIUCD was 156 (78.00%) and 43 (21.50%) respectively. No serious complication was observed in the study

Conclusion: PPIUCD insertion at public health facilities is a useful, convenient and low-cost postpartum contraceptive method.

Keywords: PPIUCD, Continuation, Outcome, Expulsion

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Weaving dreams on handloom utilizing “Manjusha art”

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Abstract

Bhagalpur, city of Bihar is famous for its weaving silk sari. Weavers here are known for their handloom weaving. But the sari weaving is not fetching the revenue to make them economically stable. From the survey it was found that there was need it's introduce innovation in this field.

In weaving, there is involvement of men. Women here are limiting themselves only to the art and craft for rituals. One of the traditional arts here is “Manjusha art “which is on verge of extinction and needs revival.

This art is done by the women. In this project efforts were made to revive Manjusha art by creating motifs and design will bring will innovation in weaving.

This project was undertaken to develop a business model which will lead to economic development thus social change, targeting

- Poverty reduction
- Women empowerment
- Community development

By this co-design project the women folk got interested and more and more women came forward to work. Though in the beginning the economic gain has not much but as this model will take up, it will certainly lead to economic development.

Key Word:-Empowerment, Co-design, handloom, Community development, poverty reduction.

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Determinants of Obesity among the Bengali Adolescents of North Bengal, West Bengal (India)

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Abstract: Obesity becomes a global pandemic for all age-groups at present time. Obesity has been found to be associated with different types of co-morbidities. The present cross-sectional study has been carried out among the Bengali adolescents of Matigara area of Darjeeling district, West Bengal. The aim of the present study was to find out the determinants of obesity among the studied adolescents. Four anthropometric measurements were taken. SPSS v.26 was used for data analysis. The prevalence of both general and central obesity has been found to be high in case of girls. Chi-square showed that number of siblings was associated with obesity among the adolescents. The other factors found to be associated with obesity were gender, birth order, mother's education and father's occupation. In conclusion it can be said that girls were more prone to be obese. Proper awareness and interventions can be helpful to reduce the burden of obesity.

Keywords: Bengali adolescents, Obesity, Waist-Hip Ratio, Waist-Height Ratio, North Bengal

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OP-44

**An Economic Analysis of Area, Yield and Production of Cotton in
India**

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Abstract: This study conducts a comprehensive economic analysis of the trends in area under cultivation, yield, and production of cotton in India, alongside evaluating the instability in these parameters from 1990 to 2023. Utilizing methodologies such as the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) and the Cuddy Della Valle Instability Index, the study quantifies growth rates and measures instability to understand the dynamics of the cotton sector. The results indicate significant fluctuations and low instability in the area under cultivation, yield, and production, influenced by technological advancements, climate change, and market volatility. Technological improvements, particularly the adoption of genetically modified (GM) cotton, have led to yield increases, albeit with regional disparities. The analysis highlights the need for climate-resilient agricultural practices, improved irrigation infrastructure, and stable policy support to enhance the sustainability and resilience of cotton farming in India. These insights are crucial for policymakers, researchers, and stakeholders to develop strategies that ensure the stability, productivity, and sustainability of the cotton sector, thereby securing the livelihoods of millions of farmers.

Keywords: cotton cultivation, yield instability, cotton production, economic analysis, genetically modified cotton, climate change, market volatility, Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR), Cuddy Della Valle Instability Index, India.

Dimension of Food Security and Measuring Food Security: A Systematic Review

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Abstract: Food is necessary for all living beings for their survival. In India, there is a large section of people suffering from food insecurity. A person is food insecure when they lack regular access to enough, safe and nutritious food for normal growth of an active and healthy life. This may be due to unavailability of food or lack of resources to obtain food or any other factors. This systematic review investigates the risk factors, consequences and effects of food insecurity in India. A systematic search is undertaken to identify factors leading to food security among the research works conducted previously at the individual and household level. The search databases includes Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed and Google Scholar. The study is reviews 30 published research works. The most common tool for measuring food insecurity is the Household Food Insecurity Access Scale (HFIAS), followed by the Household Food Security Survey Module (HFSSM), and the Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES).

Keyword: Food security, dimensions, measurement, nutritious, review

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OP-46

Estimation of the Rate of Soil Erosion in the Virma Basin Using RUSLE MODELING and Geospatial Tools

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Abstract: A solid quantitative approach is required for accurate estimation of soil erosion, which is an essential factor for controlling soil loss throughout a basin. This study evaluates the rate and spatial pattern of soil erosion in the central Indian river tributary of the Virma, part of the Betwa River basin. This has been carried out by applying the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) model in integration with geographic information systems (GIS) and remote sensing (RS). The average annual soil erosion rate (A) has been calculated to be 3.90 tons per hectare per year (t/ha/yr) by the integration of several characteristics, including the length slope (LS), support practice (P), rainfall-runoff erosion (R), cover-management (C), and soil erodibility (K). The Virma River basin's soil erosion intensity has been extensively studied through the use of the RUSLE model. The report further emphasizes on adopting conservation measures, environmentally friendly cultivation methods, and methods for soil management can help reduce soil erosion

Keywords: Soil erosion, Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) model, geographic information systems (GIS) and remote sensing (RS), conservation measures, soil management, sustainability

Effectiveness of Systemic Hydration in Speech-Language Pathologists: A Quasi-experimental Pre-post study

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Abstract

Introduction: Over the years, many professional voice users have utilized systemic hydration to achieve optimal voice quality. However still limited research on the effects of systemic hydration on voice quality measures in literature. The present study aimed to investigate the impact of systemic hydration on voice quality multidimensional, especially in Speech-Language Pathologists (SLPs).

Study Design: Quasi-experimental, pre-test, and post-test group design were applied

Methods: Twenty vocally healthy speech-language pathologists volunteered for the present study among them 10 in the control group (only vocal loading task), and 10 in the experimental group (vocal loading task along with systemic hydration). For the vocal loading task, participants have to read texts at 75-80dB SPL. Voice samples were collected on multidimensional voice parameters both before and after vocal loading tasks for both groups. The parameters included acoustic measures (MDVP), aerodynamic measures (MPD and s/z ratio), thermal measures (FT), and self-perceptual measures (PPE and PVT).

Results: The present study showed a significant difference between pre-and post-condition for the control group, especially in acoustic (STD, jitter, VF0, shimmer, APQ & NHR), aerodynamic (MPD), thermal (FT), and self-perceptual (PPE and PVT) measures. However, the experimental group (vocal loading task + systemic hydration) group did not show any significant changes in the multidimensional voice outcomes, except for the self-perceptual measure (PVT).

Conclusion: It is well known that vocal loading worsens voice quality. However, in the experimental group through systemic hydration voice quality was maintained in all

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multidimensional voice outcomes except in PVT. Hence systemic hydration has positive effects on voice quality especially in SLPs and their well-being. More research is needed with a larger sample size to confirm the results, as this is a preliminary study.

Key Words: Vocal loading, acoustic measure, multidimensional measure.

Morphometric Analysis of Kharkhai River Basin, for Fluvial Erosion Susceptibility Mapping, Kolhan District, Jharkhand using Remote Sensing and GIS Technique

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Abstract: Fluvial systems are extremely sensitive to the prevailing conditions of litho structure and tectonics. Such geomorphic systems swiftly respond to any change in the external conditioning factors in the form of morphological adjustments. Fluvial morphometric parameters are therefore, studied all over the world in order to ascertain the intensity of geomorphic processes operating in the basin. Traditionally topographic maps were employed to quantitatively evaluate these attributes. However, the method is tedious and unsuitable for the application to large and multiple basins. Since the advent of high-resolution Digital Elevation Models (DEMs), a large number of drainage basins have been studied with respect to their morphometric attributes. The present study has used these attributes (relief, surface, shape and drainage texture) for predicting the erosion susceptibility of some part of the Kolhan basin. The Shuttle Radar Topographic Mission (SRTM) DEM of 30 m resolution have been used in the analysis. Morphometric parameters i.e, stream order, stream length, bifurcation ratio, Drainage density, stream frequency, form factor, circulatory ratio, etc are calculated. The drainage area of the basin is 620 square km. and shows dendritic drainage pattern. The stream order of the basin is mainly controlled by physiographic and lithological conditions of the area. The study area is designated as a six order basin with area. The increase in stream length ratio from lower to higher order shows that the study shows the study area is reached a mature geomorphic stage.

Keywords: Fluvial Erosion Susceptibility, Morphometric Parameter, Kolhan Basin.

Larvicidal activity of *Parthenium hysterophorus* in acetone, methanol and hexane solvents against Mosquito larvae

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Abstract: Subsequently, mosquito-borne diseases increasing the higher rate of malaria, dengue, chikungunya and filariasis cases in tropical and subtropical areas including India. We have examined the larvicidal activity of *Parthenium hysterophorus* (*P. hysterophorus*) leaf extracts in the solvents of acetone, methanol and hexane against mosquitos' larvae. We have also checked the bioactivity of insecticidal phytochemicals (e.g., saponins, flavonoids, terpenoids, alkaloids and phenols) in these solvents. Soxhlet apparatus were used for the preparation in selected solvents ranging from polar to non-polar. Fully fed larva of Culicines were collected from the stagnant water at different residential areas of Gorakhpur district. After determining the mortality of larvae in a narrower range of 4 aliquots 250, 500, 750 and 1000 ppm, respectively used yielding between 50% to 95% mortality in 24, 48, 72 and 96 hours (h). We have also determined the phytochemical analysis as per standard protocols. In our study, *P. hysterophorus* were showed 100% mortality at 3000 PPM in 96 h. The acetone solvent extract showed the LC₅₀ values were 1339.26, 1285.61, 751.43, 378.16 mg/L and LC₉₀ values were 4955.80, 5977.11, 4098.80, 1331.31 mg/L in 24, 48, 72, and 96 h, respectively. However, the methanolic extract had shown the (LC₅₀: 3175.96, 1867.22, 1102.80, 312.76 mg/L; LC₉₀: 47159.39, 23832.81, 24647.56, 941.94 mg/L) followed by (LC₅₀: 1339.26, 1285.61, 751.43, 378.16 mg/L; LC₉₀: 4955.80, 5977.11, 4098.80, 1331.31 mg/L) in hexane solvent as our time dependent experiment. Our phytochemical analysis revealed that methanol extract had maximum rich in saponin, flavonoid, terpenoid, alkaloid and phenols followed by acetone however, hexane extract had only showed terpenoid and alkaloid activity. Our study showed that leaf extracts of *P. hysterophorus* exhibited maximum toxicity in acetone solvent followed by methanol and hexane against mosquito larvae.

Keywords: *Aedes aegypti*, *Parthenium hysterophorus*, Larvicidal activity, Plant Extract, Solvents.

Predictive Modeling of Land Use Land Cover Dynamics Using Multi-Temporal Satellite Data

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Abstract: Land use and land cover (LULC) changes serve as critical indicators of regional sustainability and require continuous monitoring. In this study, we focused on the Cooch Behar district in West Bengal. Our primary objectives were to estimate the area under different LULC categories, detect changes over time, and predict future LULC patterns. To achieve these goals, we utilized Landsat satellite imagery spanning three periods (2001, 2011, and 2021). The study identified six LULC classes using the Maximum Likelihood algorithm. Notably, agricultural land covered more than 60.30% of the total area, vegetation occupied 10.24%, and built-up areas accounted for 11.13%. We assessed the overall accuracy of the LULC classification by sampling 250 reference test pixels using ArcMap's stratified random sampling method. Additionally, we employed Cellular Automata and Artificial Neural Network (CA_ANN) models for prediction. Validation using the Methods of Land Use Change Evaluation (MULUSCE) module confirmed the reliability of our approach. Based on the trained model and classified LULC maps from 2011 and 2021, CA predicted the LULC map for 2031. Notably, vegetation exhibited a decline in cover, while built-up areas and agricultural land showed potential increases. Other LULC classes may experience slight reductions in their area in the future.

Keywords: Remote Sensing, Geographic Information Systems, Land Use Land Cover Change, Cellular Automata, Artificial Neural Network.

**Effectiveness of Alphamethrin and Chloropyrifos against the larva of Diamondback moth
(*Plutella xylostella* L.)**

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Abstract: Diamondback moth (DBM), *Plutella xylostella* (Plutellidae; Lepidoptera), is the major pest, inflicting significant losses to cauliflower and cabbage plants 52% yield loss in India. We attempted to identify the suitable dilutions of alphamethrin (10% EC) and chloropyrifos (20% EC) for the mortality of second instar larvae. The larva of DBM was collected from the cauliflower field in Rajahicamp, kushmahi, Gorakhpur, Uttar Pradesh, India. We have leaf disc method for toxicity bioassay was made from the cauliflower leaf from unsprayed field. After determining the mortality of larvae in a narrower range of 4 dilutions as amount 0.01, 0.03, 0.05, and 0.07% of pesticides as per assay and repeated each dilution six times, including controls for the period of 24, 48, 72 and 96, hrs (h); respectively. Alphamethrin showed the LD₅₀ values were 1077.22, 938.01, 593.56 and 270.84 ppm in 24, 48, 72, and 96 h, respectively. However, dilutions of chloropyrifos showed the LD₅₀ as 881.96, 487.78, 243.61 and 108.58 ppm in same intervals. The slopes values for larvae assessed also showed 2.60±0.56-1.18±0.26 for alphamethrin and 1.60±0.33-1.23±0.27 for chlorpyrifos from 24 h -96 h. This indicates a rapid change in mortality with increase in pesticide dosage especially the chlorpyrifos. Our study suggests that these pesticides especially chloropyrifos up to amount 500 ppm diluted solution during 48-96 hr were the sufficient dose against the DBM larva of cruciferous cultivars and minimal the insecticide resistance capability.

Key words: - Diamondback moth, Synthetic insecticide, Brassicaceae, cauliflower, Cabbage

The Impact of Social Support and Personality Traits on Postpartum Depression

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Abstract

Background: Postpartum depression (PPD) is a prevalent psychological condition affecting women after childbirth. Symptoms include despair and mood fluctuations, and the condition has become increasingly common in recent years.

Objective: This study examines the relationship between postpartum depression (PPD), social support, and personality traits, and explores the effects of mediating and moderating variables.

Methods: Data were collected from 200 women within one to two years post-childbirth using the Edinburgh Postpartum Depression Scale (EPDS), the Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS), and the Big Five Inventory-10 (BFI-10).

Results: Higher social support correlated with lower PPD symptoms. Neuroticism increased PPD risk, while extraversion reduced it. Social support mediated the impact of personality traits on PPD, buffering negative effects.

Conclusion: Social support plays a crucial role in reducing PPD, influenced by personality traits. Interventions enhancing social support and addressing personality factors can help mitigate PPD symptoms.

Photocatalytic Activity of BCN/Bi₂O₃ Nanocomposites on Textile Dye Effluent

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In this present study, Boron carbon nitride doped bismuth oxide nanocomposite has been synthesized by Calcination method. The synthesis process involved Calcination of the boron carbon nitride doped bismuth oxide nanocomposite at 500°C for 2 hours .The synthesized boron carbon nitride doped bismuth oxide was characterized using UV – Diffused reflectance spectroscopy and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy. The morphology of the synthesized boron carbon nitride was confirmed by Scanning electron microscope. The band gap of the synthesized boron carbon nitride doped bismuth oxide was determined to be 2.6 eV. The photocatalytic activity of the synthesized nanocomposite was studied by using degradation of Acid yellow 23 dye. The degradation efficiency has been studied by varying the pH of the dye solution and concentration of the dye solution. From the study maximum dye removal efficiency of 87% was observed for 20 ppm dye solution at 8 pH. These findings highlight the potential of the boron carbon nitride doped bismuth oxide nanocomposite as an effective photocatalyst for environmental remediation applications.

Keywords: Advanced oxidation process; band gap; photocatalysts; acid yellow 23; dye degradation.

Economic Value Added (EVA) – A key indicator to measure financial Performance

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Abstract: This purpose of this paper is to provide an overview of Economic Value Added as a key indicator to measure financial performance. Several large, well known business entities have begun to use EVA in recent year as an internal and external financial performance measurement. This paper shows what the EVA metric is and highlights utilization of EVA for performance measurement and advantages and disadvantages of economic value added. Now a days all business firms focused on wealth generation of their stakeholders as well itself. This EVA concept provides knowledge regarding financial performance measuring by this new value generate concept. EVA concept is basically focused on the wealth generation of business and concept provide help to financial analysis of firm. This paper provides basic idea to measure financial performance by using EVA. Now a day business entities start to think about value addition through EVA and MVA which are two elements of value addition concept. The Economic Value Added Concept helps to business and stakeholders to take necessary business decisions that help to grow a firm.

Keywords: EVA, MVA, NOPAT, WACC

HPLC analysis of Curcuminoids and flavonoids in the methanolic rhizome and leaf extracts of *Curcuma zedoaria*

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Curcuma zedoaria is a rhizomatous plant belongs to Zingiberaceae family and is well-known for its ethno-medicinal uses. The bioactive components of curcuma are mostly Alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, and phenolic compounds that possess multiple therapeutic properties. This study was designed to evaluate and compare the curcuminoids and flavonoids from the methanolic rhizome and leaf extracts of *Curcuma zedoaria* using HPLC collected from Himachal Pradesh, India. The findings showed that the curcumin was present in the rhizome at the concentration of 0.155 μ g/20 μ L whereas no amount of curcumin was detected in leaf extract. Similarly, Bismethoxycurcumin was analyzed in rhizome extract (0.013 μ g/20 μ L) and leaf showed high content of Bismethoxycurcumin (0.101 μ g/20 μ L). For Bisdemethoxycurcumin, 0.75 μ g/20 μ L was recorded in the rhizome extract whereas 0.98 μ g/20 μ L was present in leaf extract of *Curcuma zedoaria*. The flavonoid content was also investigated from both the extracts and it was revealed that 0.24 μ g/20 μ L amount of Quercetin was present in the rhizome part and 0.56 μ g/20 μ L in the leaf extract. Subsequently, rutin was present in fewer amounts (0.101 μ g/20 μ L) in rhizome extract as compared to the leaf extract (2.66 μ g/20 μ L) of *Curcuma zedoaria*. The findings show that *Curcuma zedoaria* includes a variety of bioactive components (curcuminoids and flavonoids) and is thus suggested as a phytopharmaceutical plant.

Key words: *Curcuma zedoaria*, rhizomes, phytochemicals, methanolic, curcuminoids and flavonoids

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**Quantitative Morphometric Analysis of Wah Khri Catchment, West Khasi Hills,
Meghalaya**

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Abstract: A river in any landscape plays an important role in conveying and transporting water and sediments to the low-lying areas under the influence of regional geology, lithology, tectonic setting and climatic conditions. These in turn produced different types of topography and dictates the rates and patterns of drainage networks within which rivers operate in the catchment through controls on the water distribution as well as usage of kinetic energy. Wah Khri catchment lies in the central part of Shillong Plateau which is one of the main rivers flowing in the State of Meghalaya. The river originates in the West Khasi Hills, north of Mairang town and neighbouring areas at an elevation of 1600m above mean sea level where it flows to the north direction and then entering the State of Assam in the form of Kulsi river, a tributary of Brahmaputra River. The catchment provides drinking water and for agricultural activities to sustain the livelihood of the people residing in this region. However, the clearing of forest lands to expand the agricultural activities has caused the land to deplete of its forest resources and thus eventually degrades the top soil that leads to erosion. Therefore, this leads to depletion of soil fertility. Morphometric analysis will help to understand the hydrological characteristics as well as morphological attributes of the catchment. Quantitative evaluation of morphometric parameters such as linear, areal and relief aspects using GIS techniques will be consider for the study. This will help to understand and promote proper planning for management of soil, water and forest resources for the benefit of people living in those areas. Similarly, awareness programme must be conducted for water management and forest conservation.

Keywords: Agricultural activities, Hydrological characteristics, Morphological attributes, Wah Khri catchment, Morphometric analysis

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OP-57

Toxic effect of dimethoate (organophosphates) against predatory fish *Mystus mystus*

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During past two decades the use of pesticides has increased considerably in agriculture. These pesticides are carried out aquatic ecosystem by surface runoff from sites of application, where they enter the organisms through food webs and also through contact in water. Among different classes of pesticides, organophosphates are more frequently used, because of their high insecticidal property, low mammalian toxicity, less persistence and rapid biodegradability in the environment. The Dimethoate has shown strong piscicidal activity against in freshwater fish *Mystus mystus* for all the exposure periods (24 or 96h) in time as well as dose dependent manner. The LC₅₀ values decreases from 0.028 ppm (24h) > 0.023ppm (48h) > 0.016ppm (72h) > 0.010ppm (96h) in summer season at the water temperature 25°C. The pesticide exposure may also lethal to many non-targeted organisms like fish where it hampers its health through impairment of metabolism, occasionally leading to the death of the fish.

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OP-58

Comparative Morphometric Analysis of Mahananda River Basins: Pre and Post Channel Avulsion

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Abstract: In order to perform a morphometric comparison of the Mahananda River Basin, this study differentiates between time periods preceding and following a major channel avulsion event that took place prior to the 1970s. The analysis is divided into three distinct sections: the pre-avulsion Old Mahananda River Basin, and the subsequent post-avulsion divisions consisting of the Present and Abandoned Mahananda River Basins. Using Geographic Information System (GIS) techniques, we assessed several morphometric characteristics such as drainage basin area, perimeter, relative perimeter, basin length, and the length-area relation. These parameters were analysed with respect to linear, aerial, relief, and tectonic aspects. The significant effects of avulsion on river dynamics, sediment deposition, and landscape structuring are highlighted by the substantial morphometric and topographical changes observed in the basins as a result of our research. The findings emphasise the significance of studying past alterations in river channels to comprehend present river basin structures and efficiently manage water-related resources.

Keywords: Mahananda River Basin, channel avulsion, morphometric analysis, GIS, basin geometry, hydrological changes, fluvial processes, landscape evolution.

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OP-59

Resilience Dynamics in Modeling Buruli Ulcer: A Global Stability Analysis of SEITR-SEI Model with Considerations for Relapse, Immunity Erosion, and Arsenic Contamination in Surface Water

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Abstract: Buruli ulcer, caused by the pathogen *Mycobacterium ulcerans*, manifests as a necrotizing infection affecting skin, subcutaneous tissue, and bone. Ranked as the third most prevalent mycobacterial disease by the World Health Organization (WHO), it poses significant health challenges globally. This study presents a comprehensive analysis of the transmission dynamics of *Mycobacterium ulcerans* in both humans and water bugs, employing an early non-linear mathematical model. Integrating sub-models for human and environmental populations, we address water contamination with arsenic as a contributing factor. Considering the partial immunity conferred by treatment and the potential for reinfection, we explore two treatment strategies: for the actively infected human population and the latently infected population. The model reveals two equilibrium points: one representing a Buruli-free state and the other indicating the presence of the disease. Local stability analysis around the disease-free equilibrium, characterized by the basic reproduction number (R_0), unveils a forward transcritical bifurcation near $R_0 = 1$. Global stability analysis further confirms that when $R_0 \leq 1$, the disease-free equilibrium is globally asymptotically stable, whereas a globally asymptotically stable endemic equilibrium emerges for $R_0 > 1$. Numerical simulations illustrate the dynamic interplay, highlighting the beneficial impact of treatment on disease transmission dynamics.

Key words: Arsenic, Water bugs, *Mycobacterium ulcerans*, Buruli Ulcer, Basic reproduction number, Local stability analysis, Global stability analysis.

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Synthesis, characterization and application of Chitosan nanoparticles for degradation of organic dyes

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Rapid industrialization and modernization have introduced substantial amounts of toxic heavy metals into the aquatic and terrestrial environments, posing a serious threat to flora and fauna. Considerable research has been conducted and is ongoing regarding natural biopolymers and their modifications to remove various heavy metals, toxic dyes and antibiotics. Among these, chitosan and cellulose, both naturally occurring polysaccharides, are highly effective for removing these toxic materials from wastewater. Chitosan, derived from the N-deacetylation of chitin, consists of glucosamine and N-acetylglucosamine units. It has garnered extensive attention for its biocompatibility, biodegradability, mucoadhesiveness, and derivation from abundant and inexpensive biomass. Moreover, chitosan's antibacterial nature, non-toxicity, and biodegradability make it suitable for producing biodegradable films as green alternatives to synthetic counterparts. The purpose of this study is to outline the synthetic procedure for a novel photocatalyst, nano-chitosan, designed for the effective photodegradation of Congo red dyes, used in textile industry and ciprofloxacin (CF), a widely used antibiotic in poultry farming. The synthesis of chitosan was characterized using FT-IR, XRD, SEM, EDS, and BET N₂ adsorption isotherm techniques. The surface area, pore volume, and pore radius were measured at 13.61 m²/g, 0.026 mL/g, and 13.5 nm, respectively. The studies revealed that degradation followed first-order kinetics, with the optimum pH for the degradation process identified as 6.0, achieving a maximum degradation efficiency of 97.0% and 99% for Ciprofloxacin, Congo red respectively.

Furthermore, chitosan's reusability over five consecutive cycles highlights its potential for removing and degrading CF from aquatic environments.

Key words-Chitosan, Photodegradation, Nano photocatalyst, Congo red dye, ciprofloxacin

Environmentally Friendly Fabrication and Analysis of Calcium Cross-Linked Carboxymethyl Chitosan Nanoparticles: Application as an Efficient Sorbent for Cd(II) Ion Removal

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This study explores the synthesis and application of carboxymethyl chitosan nanoparticles (cm-CHNPs) as an effective adsorbent for the removal of heavy metal ions, specifically Cd (II), from aqueous solutions. The nanoparticles were prepared using Coconut Nectar as a stabilizing agent and calcium ions as a cross-linking agent, resulting in well-defined crystalline nanoparticles with a size range of 10-100 nm. Characterization techniques, including TEM, SEM, SAED, and FTIR, confirmed the successful formation and structure of cm-CHNPs. The adsorption behaviour of cm-CHNPs was investigated through batch adsorption experiments, focusing on the effects of initial metal ion concentration, contact time, and adsorbent dosage. The equilibrium data was analysed using various isotherm models, and the kinetic data was evaluated using pseudo-first-order and pseudo-second-order models. The results showed that cm-CHNPs exhibit excellent adsorption capacity for Cd (II) ions, with maximum adsorption capacities ranging from 205.6 to 231.25 mg/g according to Langmuir and Sips isotherm models, respectively. The adsorption process followed pseudo second-order kinetics, indicating chemisorption as the dominant mechanism for Cd (II) removal. Overall, cm-CHNPs demonstrated remarkable potential as a promising adsorbent material for the efficient removal of Cd (II) from water, with implications for heavy metal pollution control and water treatment applications. These findings contribute valuable insights into the design of effective sorption systems using nanomaterials for environmental remediation.

Keywords: Nanomaterial; Green synthesis; Carboxymethyl chitosan; Sorption; cadmium removal; water purification

Cellulose Bio Whiskers For Removal Of Uranium From Industrial Waste Water

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A novel adsorbent, nanocellulose bio-whiskers with multi-carboxyl functional groups, was developed for the effective removal of uranium (U) from aqueous solutions. The adsorbent underwent characterization using FTIR, XRD, SEM-EDS, TEM, AFM, and potentiometric titrations before and after adsorption of U ions. Surface morphological changes were observed through SEM images, revealing structural alterations post-adsorption. The effect of various parameters such as initial metal concentration, pH, contact time, temperature and adsorbent dose on sorption process was investigated in batch mode technique. The optimal pH was determined to be 6.0, and an adsorbent dose of 1.5 g/L was found sufficient for complete removal of U from a 100 mg/L solution at room temperature. Kinetic studies revealed that the adsorption of U followed a pseudo-second-order model. Isotherm studies were conducted, and data were analysed using Langmuir, Freundlich, and Sips isotherm models, with the Sips model demonstrating the best fit. Desorption experiments using 0.1 M HCl showed that the adsorbent could be reused for six cycles without significant loss in performance. The practical efficacy of the adsorbent was tested using nuclear industrial wastewater.

Key words: Nano cellulose, Bio Whiskers, Uranium ion, Adsorption, Nano Adsorbent, Kinetic Models.

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OP-63

Initiatives to Improve Status of Teachers

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Abstract: Teaching is a Profession that is evolving from Vedic Period considered as a Guru. The status of Teachers is a matter of concern because it is declining. Teachers are very essential to the educational structure. They act as a guiding force, a support system, that help students learn, grow, and become successful individuals. NEP 2020 recommended 50 hours of compulsory training to in- service teachers every year. From recent studies it can be found that many teachers don't find this job interesting or there are many problems in terms of recruitment no fixed Cycle, no clear guidelines but there are many organizations that work very effectively for the improvement of Teachers and there are certain applications also which can help in the management of work of teachers that can reduce their stress. Sample taken were Pre- Service and in- service teachers. Focus group discussions are being done and data is collected through Google forms. Major findings were there are lack of Training and certain factors are found due to which Status of Teachers are affected. Various initiatives such as Continuous Professional Development through DIKSHA Portal can be beneficial.

Keywords: Teachers, Professionalism, NEP 2020, Initiatives, DIKSHA, Continuous Professional Development

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OP-64

Unlocking the Potential of Kombucha: Probiotic Fermented Foods for Gut Health and Beyond

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Abstract: This article explores the impact of probiotic fermented foods on human health, focusing on the probiotic beverage Kombucha. The current study emphasizes the significance of gut microbiota in human health, role in digestion, nutrient absorption, and immune function. Kombucha, a traditional fermented beverage, is introduced as a popular probiotic option, with historical origins and rising commercial availability.

The composition and diversity of gut microbiota were examined, along with factors influencing microbial balance such as diet, medication, and lifestyle. The concept and benefits of probiotic fermented foods are elucidated, including improved digestion, enhanced immune function, and potential mental health benefits. The importance of probiotic strain diversity in fermented foods is emphasized.

The origins, ingredients, fermentation process, and nutritional profile of Kombucha are detailed, providing insights into its potential health effects. Studies on the impact of Kombucha consumption on gut microbiota composition and therapeutic effects on digestive disorders are reviewed.

Furthermore, the immune-modulating, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties of Kombucha are discussed, along with precautions for vulnerable populations. Safety considerations associated with homemade Kombucha preparation and guidelines for safe consumption of commercially available products are provided.

The article concludes with a call for continued research and awareness in the field of probiotics and fermented foods, emphasizing evidence-based recommendations for Kombucha consumption and opportunities for collaboration between researchers, industry stakeholders, and healthcare professionals.

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Keywords: Probiotic Fermented Foods, Gut Microbiota, Kombucha, Health Benefits, Microbial Diversity, Fermentation Process, Safety Considerations

Study of magnetic field on strange quark matter

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Abstract: The main aim is to compute the thermodynamic observables of strange quark matter in the presence of a magnetic field using a theoretical approach. We employ a quasiparticle model to enhance our ability to calculate the equation of state for strange quark matter under strong magnetic fields. Through this quasiparticle framework, we analyze the equation of state to explore various properties of strange quark stars across different magnetic field strengths, while accounting for relevant factors. References

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OP-66

Zinc Oxide Synthesis from Fruit peel waste for wastewater treatment

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Abstract

The generation and utilization of fruit waste have become critical in recent years due to environmental concerns and the need for sustainable waste management. This study focuses on the synthesis of zinc oxide (ZnO) from orange and pineapple peels, using precipitation method to optimize the process. The synthesized ZnO was evaluated for its effectiveness as a photocatalyst in wastewater treatment, targeting pollutants like methylene blue dye and imidacloprid insecticides individually. By converting food waste into valuable ZnO, this approach addresses waste disposal issues while offering an eco-friendly solution for water purification. Key synthesis parameters including various types of precursor and calcination temperature were systematically varied to maximize the quality of ZnO. Results demonstrated that ZnO derived from fruit peels exhibited high degradation rates for methylene blue and imidacloprid under optimized conditions. Effect of various parameters on imidacloprid removal was also analysed. This study underscores the potential of bio-derived ZnO as an efficient photocatalyst for hazardous pollutant treatment in wastewater, advancing both environmental sustainability and resource efficiency.

Keywords: Zinc Oxide, Fruit Peel, Wastewater treatment, Photocatalyst, waste utilization

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OP-67

In-silico Study of Phytochemicals of Asparagus racemose and Trifolium Pratense for Anti-cancer Potential.

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Abstract: It has long been known that plants are abundant in bioactive substances, many of which have anti-cancer qualities. These substances, referred to as phytochemicals, have a variety of chemical configurations and modes of action. Alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, and polyphenols are a few examples. Researchers can investigate the binding interactions of these phytochemicals with certain protein targets linked to the initiation and progression of cancer by using molecular docking experiments.

Numerous bioactive substances found in these plants have the ability to interact with particular proteins involved in cancer pathways. Comprehending the correlation between these compounds' binding energies and their affinity for proteins linked to cancer is crucial for the creation of efficacious anti-cancer medications.

A review paper on “Comparative Study of Essential Oil Extraction from Spices and Herbs”

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Abstract: The application of essential oil is increased because of the adverse effect of synthetic chemicals used in food preservation, cosmetic products and medicines on human and environment. The bioactive compounds present in the essential oil possess the antioxidant, antimicrobial and antifungal activities which are used in the food preservation, ayurvedic medicines, pain relief oil, mosquito repellents, etc. The natural phytochemicals present in the plant materials such as the thymol in ajwain and menthol from peppermint used in the mouthwash. The citral content in the lemongrass used as the mosquito repellents while eucalyptol present in eucalyptus and the piperine in the black pepper used as the anti-inflammatory agent and in respiratory disorder diseases. The extraction of these volatiles, present in the plant materials is essential. The hydro-distillation is commonly used to extract the essential oil while the microwave assisted extraction and ultrasound assisted extraction are the non-conventional methods used to get high extraction yield and good quality of the oil. This review paper comprise of the study of the effect of extraction methods on the different plant material and the variation of process conditions such as type of solvent, pre-treatment process and time.

Keywords: Essential Oils (EOs), Hydro-distillation (HD), Microwave assisted Extraction (MAE), Microwave assisted hydro-distillation (MAHD), Ultrasound assisted extraction (UAE)

Isolation of beneficial microbes from rice (Joha) rhizosphere

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Abstract: Rice is one of the most popular and important cereal grains, also known as “global grain” is an excellent source of carbohydrate and energy. Rice is a rich source of carbohydrate, consisting of protein, fat, and vitamins. The four main categories of rice of Assam are: Sali rice (winter rice), Ahu rice (Autumn rice), Boro rice (summer rice), Bao rice (deepwater rice). The aromatic or scented rice of Assam is a unique class under Sali rice, traditionally known as “Joha”. It has its unique aroma and due to this aroma, it is very popular and has high demand in the market and is used mainly for the preparation of special dishes like kheer and pulao. In this study, rhizospheric soil of Joha rice were collected for performing different experiment. This study was performed for the isolation, evaluation, identification and characterization of microbes present in the rhizosphere and endo-rhizosphere of collected soil and root sample of Joha rice. Isolation of rhizosphere microbes from the soil sample was done by serial dilution method and the isolation of endo-rhizosphere microbes from the root sample was done by grinding method after surface sterilization. Morphological and biochemical properties of the isolated bacteria were also studied. The Gram’s staining result of the isolated bacteria were found to be both gram-positive and gram-negative. Starch hydrolysis test, urease utilizing test, phosphate solubilization test, zinc solubilization test, indole acetic acid test of the fungal isolates was also done for the better understanding of PGPR activities. Observation of fungal isolates by fungal staining shows similarity with *Aspergillus*. Molecular investigation by using 16S gene amplification and 18S gene amplification for bacterial and fungal isolates were also done and amplification was seen. Further investigation using sequencing technique would finally be helpful in identification up to species level.

Keywords: Joha rice, aromatic rice, Assam, rhizosphere, rhizoplane, Beneficial Microbes, PGPR

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OP-70

**A STUDY ON THE EFFECTIVENESS AND PERFORMANCE OF UZHAVAR
SANTHAI IN CHENGALPATTU DISTRICT**

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The Uzhavar Santhai initiative, introduced by former Chief Minister M. Karunanidhi in 1999, stands as one of Tamil Nadu's most significant schemes aimed at bridging the gap between farmers and consumers through direct marketing. This research paper examines the performance and effectiveness of Uzhavar Santhai in the Chengalpattu district, with a particular focus on five markets situated in regions with minimal agricultural activity. While direct marketing is a globally recognized practice, the Uzhavar Santhai scheme is specifically tailored to transform traditional market dynamics within Tamil Nadu. The initiative primarily targets areas with substantial agricultural engagement; however, its implementation has expanded to approximately 180 locations, including those with lesser agricultural prevalence. This study aims to evaluate the operational efficiency and economic contributions of these selected Uzhavar Santhai outlets in non-agricultural regions. By analyzing their impact on the local economy, the research provides valuable insights into the broader applicability and effectiveness of the Uzhavar Santhai model. The findings are expected to inform future policy decisions and strategic implementations to enhance the scheme's reach and efficacy, particularly in regions not traditionally associated with intensive agriculture.

Keywords: Uzhavar Santhai, direct marketing, Tamil Nadu, agricultural markets, non-agricultural regions, policy evaluation, rural development.

**Isolation and identification of endophytes from the orchid (*Cymbidium dayanum*)
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Abstract: Endophytic microorganisms frequently serve a variety of purposes in plants, including transporting nutrients from the soil into plants, controlling plant growth, enhancing plants' ability to withstand stress, reducing virulence pathogen, enhancing plants' ability to resist disease, and preventing the emergence of rival plant species. Orchids are known to have a unique relationship with endophytic fungi. The association between them is a fascinating example of the complex relationships that can exist between different organisms in nature. Researchers have already identified several different types of endophytic bacteria associated with orchids. Some of such endophytic microbes have been shown to produce growth-promoting compounds. *Cymbidium dayanum* is considered valuable specimens because of its lengthy flowering season and exquisite plant. In this study, endophyte associated with leaves of *Cymbidium dayanum* were isolated, characterized and preliminary identification studies were done. The isolation was done using three media and by two methods namely grinding and placing technique after surface sterilization of leaf samples. After isolation of the pure colonies, the morphological and biochemical characterization studies were done for both bacterial and fungal endophytes. Starch hydrolysis test, urease utilizing test, phosphate solubilization test, zinc solubilization test, indole acetic acid test of the fungal isolates was also done for the better understanding of PGPR activities. Lastly, 16S and 18S gene amplification was done for bacterial and fungal isolates, respectively. Further investigation using sequencing technique would finally be helpful in identification up to species level. This study lay the foundation for further analysis in characterizing the endophytes of *Cymbidium dayanum*.

Keywords: Endophyte, Orchid, *Cymbidium*, epiphytes, Threatened Orchid, Assam, Beneficial Microbes

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OP-72

UNEXPLAINED INFERTILITY:- Causes and Optimal ART

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Abstract: The half of the couple population are looking for medical assistance for infertility are diagnosed with unexplained infertility. This condition put forward a challenge to choose the optimal treatment approach. The at hand treatments are IUI and IVF, but guidelines vary for each other. Forecasting- based management is recognized as research priority and various prediction models have been innovated to guide the optimal treatment decision. However, there is a rift between research evidence and its clinical practice. In this particular write-up, we go into the circumstances of unexplained infertility, focus on its potential to improve clinical practice.

Keywords: unexplained infertility, intra- uterine insemination, in-vitro fertilization, forecasting-based management.

A Comparative Study of debate speech analysis using Argumentation Mining in LLMs

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Abstract:

Argument mining (AM) refers to the automated extraction of arguments, their components, and/or relationships from natural language text. The general AM problem can be divided into three primary tasks:

- 1) argument identification, which entails segmenting text into units and determining which are argumentative;
- 2) identification of argumentative components, typically involving the classification of claims and/or premises in argumentative text; and
- 3) identification of argumentative relations, which aims to determine how different texts are related within argumentative discourse.

Argument mining (AM) involves automatically extracting arguments, their elements, and/or relationships from text. With the proliferation of platforms facilitating online debates, the demand for AM is increasingly pressing, particularly to support subsequent tasks. Relation-based AM (RbAM) specifically targets the identification of agreement (support) and disagreement (attack) relationships among arguments. However, RbAM poses a formidable classification challenge, with current methods often falling short of satisfactory performance. In this study, we demonstrate that general-purpose Large Language Models (LLMs), when appropriately primed and prompted, can significantly surpass the performance of the best existing baseline (RoBERTa-based). This extensive review aims to provide focus on two open-source LLMs (Llama-2 and Mistral) across ten datasets.

Keywords: Relation-based AM, Argument mining, Large Language Models, Llama-2, Mistral

Sentiment Analysis in recognizing emotional tone of text

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Abstract: Sentiment analysis, a key method in natural language processing, evaluates and identifies the emotional tone in textual data. By analyzing words and phrases, it categorizes sentiments as positive, negative, or neutral. This process is crucial for extracting valuable insights from large text datasets, enabling businesses to understand customer feelings, make informed decisions, and improve their products and services. To further advance sentiment analysis, it is essential to have a thorough understanding of its algorithms, applications, current performance, and challenges. This comprehensive survey explores the wide range of application domains for sentiment analysis, reviewing them in the context of existing research. We examine common pre-processing techniques, datasets, and evaluation metrics to deepen understanding. Additionally, we investigate the roles of Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Large Language Models, and Pre-trained models in sentiment analysis, highlighting their benefits and limitations. We then critically review experimental results and the limitations of recent state-of-the-art studies. Finally, we discuss various challenges in sentiment analysis and suggest future research directions to address these issues. This extensive review aims to provide a complete understanding of sentiment analysis, including its models, application domains, results analysis, challenges, and potential research avenues.

Keywords: Sentiment analysis, Natural language processing, Sentiments, Pre-processing technique, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Large Language Models

PHOTOBIMODULATION IN THE TREATMENT OF XEROSTOMIA (DRY MOUTH)- AN APPRAISAL

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Abstract: Xerostomia or dry mouth is a common condition encountered in dental clinical practice. It could be a manifestation of several underlying causes like Sjogren's syndrome, or even due to high dose radiation therapy in cancer patients. This can pose an array of challenges to the ones suffering from it, including difficulty in day-to-day activities like chewing, swallowing and talking. A high incidence of caries is also seen because of xerostomia. Conventional treatment modalities for xerostomia use artificial salivary substitutes or salivary stimulants. In recent years, low-level laser therapy has been known to have a biomodulation effect on human tissues. This property, in the form of photobiomodulation has been applied in the treatment of several dental ailments like oral lichen planus, reducing post operative pains, treatment of herpetic stomatitis, aphthous ulcers and other such problems. In cases of xerostomia, photobiomodulation can be used to improve the condition of the patient using low level lasers, thus making it an effective and non-invasive treatment modality. It is safe enough to be used in even paediatric patients and has great scope in the future. Despite the endless applications of laser therapy in dentistry, studies on the use of photobiomodulation in the treatment of xerostomia remain sparse. This necessitates exploration of this treatment modality. It could potentially become a permanent treatment for this condition regardless of its etiology. This review aims to explore the efficacy and potential of photobiomodulation in the treatment of xerostomia in comparison with other treatment modalities.

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RNA interference

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Abstract: RNA interference (RNAi) is a powerful and precise biological process used to regulate gene expression by neutralizing specific mRNA molecules. RNA interference (RNAi) is a crucial post-transcriptional regulatory mechanism that involves sequence-specific gene silencing. This review highlights the mechanism of RNAi, which involves the cleavage of double-stranded RNA into small interfering RNAs (siRNAs) by the enzyme Dicer. These siRNAs are then incorporated into the RNA-induced silencing complex (RISC), guiding the complex to complementary mRNA targets for degradation. RNAi has revolutionized functional genomics and therapeutic research by allowing targeted gene silencing, offering potential treatments for viral infections, genetic disorders, and cancers. The review also addresses the challenges of RNAi delivery and off-target effects, as well as recent advancements in improving the specificity and efficiency of RNAi-based applications. This review also explores the RNAi pathway, where double-stranded RNA (dsRNA) is processed by the enzyme Dicer into small interfering RNAs (siRNAs). These siRNAs are then incorporated into the RNA-induced silencing complex (RISC), guiding the complex to degrade complementary mRNA targets, thereby preventing protein synthesis. The review discusses the significant impact of RNAi on functional genomics and its therapeutic potential in treating diseases such as viral infections, genetic disorders, and cancers. Furthermore, it examines the technical challenges associated with RNAi, including effective delivery methods and minimizing off-target effects. Recent advancements aimed at enhancing RNAi efficiency and specificity are also highlighted, underscoring the promising future of RNAi in research and medicine.

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OP-77

Hemostatic agents used in wound healing

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Abstract: For the management of wounds in a variety of patient situations, the development of efficient hemostatic agents is essential. This work focuses on developing and refining next-generation hemostatic medicines with improved safety and effectiveness profiles. To find the ideal composition for each formulation, a methodical optimization strategy was used, taking into account variables including viscosity, adhesive qualities, and hemostatic efficiency. Utilizing both in vitro and in vivo models, the produced hemostatic drugs were assessed. The haemostatic efficacy and antibacterial activity were assessed as part of the in vitro evaluation. The haemostatic efficacy, biocompatibility, and wound healing qualities of the improved formulations were evaluated in vivo using animal models.

Next-generation hemostatic drugs with enhanced safety profiles and hemostatic performance were effectively designed and optimized in this work. The combinations demonstrated outstanding wound healing potential, antibacterial qualities, and clotting ability. These results demonstrate the discovered hemostatic drugs' potential usefulness in clinical practice, especially when it comes to controlling bleeding in different healthcare environments. To determine the therapeutic application of the observed effects and to investigate the processes behind them, more research is necessary. By efficiently reducing bleeding and encouraging quick wound healing, the improved haemostatic medications have the potential to greatly improve patient outcomes.

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OP-78

Effects of Heatwaves On Human Health And Its Mitigation

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Abstract

Heatwaves are defined as extended periods of abnormally high temperatures, and they seriously endanger human health. The many effects of heatwaves are examined in this essay, including dehydration, heat exhaustion, heat stroke, respiratory and cardiovascular disorders, mental health difficulties, and a rise in mortality, especially for vulnerable groups. Mitigation strategies that are effective are necessary to lower these health hazards. These include community support activities like cooling centers and check-in programmes, public health preparedness with early warning systems and public education, and urban planning techniques to mitigate urban heat islands through greater green areas and reflective materials. Healthcare systems also need to adjust by providing enough medical supplies and training for staff, and it's important for individuals to take personal safety precautions like wearing suitable clothing, staying inside during the hottest parts of the day, and drinking plenty of water. Improving community resistance to heatwaves also requires government regulations, such as updated building rules and thorough heat action plans. Heatwaves can have a major positive impact on health when these methods are put into practice.

Synthesis and Characterization of some Chalcogen atom bearing Molecules

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Abstract

We have developed a series of SeCSe pincer ligands through the insertion nucleophilic substitution route. In this process we are able to isolate SeCSe pincer ligands in good to excellent yield. These compounds are well characterised with the help of several spectroscopic techniques.

Scheme 1: Synthesis of Pincer Ligands

Keywords: Organoselenium, Selenium, Insertion, Nucleophilic, Pincer Ligand

OP-80

Role of AI in marketing research

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is transforming market research by enhancing data collection, analysis, and interpretation processes, leading to more accurate and actionable insights. AI-driven tools such as machine learning algorithms, natural language processing (NLP), and predictive analytics are revolutionizing how businesses understand market dynamics and consumer behavior. These technologies enable the efficient handling of large datasets, uncover hidden patterns, and predict future trends with greater precision. AI facilitates real-time data analysis, allowing for timely decision-making and adaptive strategies. Additionally, AI-powered sentiment analysis provides deeper insights into consumer opinions and brand perception by analyzing social media, reviews, and other textual data sources. Automation of repetitive tasks, such as survey administration and data cleansing, increases operational efficiency and reduces costs. Overall, AI's integration in market research empowers companies to gain a competitive edge through enhanced strategic planning, personalized marketing, and improved customer experiences. As AI continues to evolve, its role in market research is expected to expand, driving further innovation and efficacy in understanding and meeting market demands.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Market research, Machine learning algorithms, Natural language processing (NLP), Predictive analytics, Data collection, Data analysis, Consumer behavior, Real-time data analysis, Sentiment analysis.

E-commerce and its Influence on Market Efficiency: An Economic Analysis

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Abstract

This research investigates the economic impact of Edge Computing and Scalable Information Systems in E-Commerce, aiming to fill a critical research gap. While existing studies have explored the effects of either Edge Computing or Scalable Information Systems in isolation, this study adopts a comprehensive approach to assess the combined impact of both technologies. Through a mixed-method research design involving quantitative data analysis and interviews with key stakeholders from five E-Commerce companies, the study uncovers significant insights. Findings reveal that the integration of Edge Computing enhances responsiveness, operational efficiency, cost savings, data security, and customer retention, while Scalable Information Systems facilitate flexible management of rapid business growth. These technologies emerge as vital assets in enhancing company performance and competitiveness within the dynamic E-Commerce landscape. This study contributes valuable insights into the synergistic effects of Edge Computing and Scalable Information Systems, offering practical implications for E-Commerce businesses seeking to leverage technology for sustainable growth.

Keyword- Edge Computing, Scalable Information Systems, E-Commerce, Economic Impact, Business Growth Management, Technological Integration

OP-82

Seasonal abundance and diversity in waterbird community of Paharni Talav (Pond), near Nagbhid Maharashtra, India

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Abstract

The present study was undertaken to explore seasonal fluctuations in density and diversity in and around the study area. The study area, Paharni Talav (Pond) (20°66'14.17"N latitude and 79°71'92.43"E longitude) is located near Nagbhid in the eastern Vidarbha region of Maharashtra. The avian survey was conducted by monthly visiting to the study site, while sampling of waterbirds were carried out according to the methodology of point transect method. In the present survey on avian community at Paharni Talav (pond) spanning the period from November 2022 to October 2023, recorded waterbirds which belongs to 37 species, 13 families and 6 orders. Seasonal fluctuations of waterbird community at Pandav Talav (Pond) indicates that, total density of water birds peaked during winter season (94.9602 ind.ha⁻¹) followed by the monsoon (55.6587 ind.ha⁻¹) and summer season (42.5729 ind.ha⁻¹). Mean abundance of waterbird community fluctuates during different seasons, waterbirds belonging to Order – Charadiiformes recorded maximum abundance (28%) followed by Pelicaniformes (24%) and Anseriformes (22%). Recorded waterbird community shows seasonal fluctuations, maximum species (N=37) recorded during winter season (Nov-Feb.) followed by summer (N=33) while monsoon season recorded minimal species (N=28). (Table.1). Data on relative abundance (RA) of different waterbird community reveals that, Cattle Egret, *Bubulcus ibis*, recorded maximum abundance throughout all the seasons, followed by little cormorant. Data on density (D) of waterbirds during present study also reveals same trend as that of relative abundance. Waterbirds mostly belongs to Ord-Anseriformes peaked during the month of December and January in other wetlands were found lacking with an exceptions of Gadwal and Northern Pintail. Developing effective measures for conservation of waterbirds in Paharni Talav (Pond) in future will depends critically on understanding current status.

Key Words – Waterbird, , Ardeidae, Charadiformes, Anatidae

Curcuma longa: A treasurer of health

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Abstract:

Curcuma longa, a member of the Zingiberaceae (ginger) family. The crop is cultivated in the tropical and subtropical regions around the world. It originates from China, Taiwan, Sri Lanka, Bangladesh, Burma (Myanmar), Nigeria, Australia, West Indies, Peru, Jamaica, and some other Caribbean and Latin American countries. India is the largest producer of turmeric. Turmeric is considered as an Indian Medicine and is a part of religious rituals. Turmeric contains more than 100 chemical compounds that contribute to its healing abilities. It is a perennial plant having short stems with large oblong leaves and bears ovate, pyriform, or oblong rhizomes, which are often branched and brownish-yellow in color. Turmeric contains 67.38% carbohydrates, 8.92% moisture, 2.85 % ash, 4.60% crude fiber, 6.85% fat, and 9.40% crude protein. Turmeric rhizome contains 0.89% thiamine, 0.16% riboflavin & 2.30% niacin. The diverse applications of turmeric include use in dietary spice, foods, textile industries, medicinal and nutraceutical fields. Components of turmeric are named curcuminoids, which include mainly curcumin (diferuloylmethane), demethoxycurcumin and bis-demethoxycurcumin. Antioxidant properties have been proven and proposed as a complementary treatment for Alzheimer's, diabetes, asthma, stomach ulcers, etc. Due to its extraordinary molecular structure, it shows strong anti-oxidative, as well as anti-inflammatory properties activities of turmeric, including anti-cancerous, antibacterial, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, antitumor, antioxidant, antiseptic, cardioprotective, hepatoprotective, nephroprotective, radioprotective and digestive activities.

Keywords: Curcuma, demethoxycurcumin and nutraceutical fields

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OP-84

Bridging Ayush and Contemporary Health Systems: The Imperative for Interdisciplinary Research Approach

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Abstract

The convergence of Ayurveda, Yoga, Unani, Siddha, and Homeopathy with contemporary health systems presents a promising avenue for improving healthcare outcomes. This abstract advocates for interdisciplinary research between AYUSH and modern medical practices to harness their complementary strengths. By integrating traditional knowledge systems with evidence-based approaches, interdisciplinary research can foster innovations in preventive care, treatment modalities, and holistic wellness. Such collaborations offers a unique opportunity to address complex health challenges, enhances patient-centered care, and promote health equity. Through case studies and theoretical frameworks, this abstract highlights the thrust areas for interdisciplinary research as an urgent need to leverage the rich heritage of AYUSH alongside advancements in modern healthcare, ultimately paving the way for a more comprehensive and integrative approach to healthcare delivery.

Keywords: AYUSH, Unani, Interdisciplinary Research, Contemporary Medicine, traditional medicine

LIVED EXPERIENCES OF MALE INMATES IN SELECTED PRISON OF MADHYA PRADESH: PILOT STUDY

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Abstract Background:

This study investigated the lived experiences of male inmates in district prison of Morena, Madhya Pradesh using phenomenological approach of qualitative research. The aim of the study was to explore lived experiences of male inmates and to find out association between type of crime and selected demographic variables. Methodology: the data were gathered through in-depth interviews focusing on the inmates' perception related to their lived experiences in prison analysis of verbatim gathered from interviews, was done using Colaizzi (seven step method) thematic analysis. Results: the themes identified were social factors with subthemes of loss and away from loved ones, and loneliness; further physical wellbeing themes and subthemes being food and environment; family support theme and subthemes emotional challenges and family care absences; finance theme and subtheme were financial loss and absence in meeting obligation. Saturation of data was achieved at 10 samples. The researcher also found positive association between type of crime and previous occupation $\chi^2=0.05$ (95% CI: 10 – 46.7), N/df (30/4, P=0.05)., history of physical diseases $\chi^2=0.001$ (95% CI: 3.3 – 96.7), N/df (30/1, P=0.05). and psychological diseases $\chi^2=0.001$ (95% CI: 3.3 – 96.7), N/df (30/1, P=0.05). Conclusion: the study concluded that there was a need to look into aspects of life among male inmates where they need a holistic approach towards their stay in prison. Further, the results help in identifying the areas of approached care which may enhance their positive perception towards life.

Keywords – Male inmates, Qualitative research, Perception, Lived experiences, Holistic approach

Quality Assurance and Quality Control for Analysis of Food and Food Products

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Abstract

Food safety and quality are paramount in the food industry to ensure public health and consumer satisfaction. This review paper explores the critical role of food standards and quality control laboratory testing in upholding these principles. The paper begins by defining food standards and regulations at both international and national levels, highlighting the responsibilities of food regulatory bodies. It then delves into the concept of quality control (QC) and its objectives within the industry, emphasizing its significance in guaranteeing food safety, quality, and consistency. Food safety and quality assurance are critical components of public health, influencing consumer trust and global food markets. This paper explores contemporary advancements and methodologies in food safety and quality assurance, highlighting innovative technologies, regulatory frameworks, and best practices. The research delves into the application of block chain technology for traceability, the role of predictive microbiology in risk assessment, and the impact of stringent international standards on food quality. A detailed examination of laboratory testing methods is provided, covering microbiological, chemical, and physical analyses used to assess various parameters such as microbial contamination, chemical residues, and nutritional content. The importance of sampling techniques is also discussed to ensure accurate and representative results. Case studies illustrate successful implementation of quality assurance programs across various sectors, emphasizing the synergy between technological innovation and regulatory compliance. The findings underscore the necessity for continuous improvement and adaptation in the face of evolving food safety challenges, advocating for a proactive approach to ensure the integrity of the food supply chain. This paper contributes to the discourse on food safety by providing a comprehensive overview of current trends and offering recommendations for future research and policy development.

Keywords—Quality, assurance, consumer, industry, food, safety, microbiology

Screening and Identification of Microbes and Responsible Enzymes for Biodegradation of Dyes

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Abstract

The dyes are highly polluting water bodies, which is a major worldwide concern. The various industries such as textile, leather, etc are releasing dyes in water bodies and polluting the environment. It is a high need to find a promising solution to treat the dyes so as to overcome with the problem of water pollution. In present study the screening of potential microbes its gene and protein was done for dye degradation. The primary screening of microorganisms responsible for dye degradation was done through Literature Survey. The gene and its responsible protein for biodegrading of dyes were identified through NCBI and Uniprot databases. The homologous gene and protein responsible for dye biodegradation was screened by using BLAST and BLASTp tool respectively. The various genes identified for the biodegradation of dyes are tmr2, ahpF, BWR15_19115 and Lcc1. The triphenylmethane reductase, alkyl hydroperoxide reductase subunit F and Laccase protein were found responsible for the biodegradation of dyes. The molecular docking of identified proteins were done against the selected dyes. These analyses help to screen the high potential protein along with its gene and microbes that are responsible for dye degradation. The *Delftia* was analysed as the main branch among identified microbes through phylogenetic analysis. These identified microorganisms can be a great help for the wet laboratory study in finding suitable microorganisms for potentially effective biodegradation of selected Dyes.

Keywords: dyes, biodegradation, protein, gene, microorganism, Laccase,

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OP-88

Bridging Ayush and Contemporary Health Systems: The Imperative for Interdisciplinary Research Approach

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Abstract

The convergence of Ayurveda, Yoga, Unani, Siddha, and Homeopathy with contemporary health systems presents a promising avenue for improving healthcare outcomes. This abstract advocates for interdisciplinary research between AYUSH and modern medical practices to harness their complementary strengths. By integrating traditional knowledge systems with evidence-based approaches, interdisciplinary research can foster innovations in preventive care, treatment modalities, and holistic wellness. Such collaborations offers a unique opportunity to address complex health challenges, enhances patient-centered care, and promote health equity. Through case studies and theoretical frameworks, this abstract highlights the thrust areas for interdisciplinary research as an urgent need to leverage the rich heritage of AYUSH alongside advancements in modern healthcare, ultimately paving the way for a more comprehensive and integrative approach to healthcare delivery.

Keywords: AYUSH, Unani, Interdisciplinary Research, Contemporary Medicine, traditional medicine

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OP-89

THE IMPACT OF MAKE IN INDIA FOR THE SKILL DEVELOPMENT IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Agriculture has been neglected most of these years. investment, if any, has been centered at low-productive units and mis-targeted subsidiaries. minimum support prices (MSP) for crops given to farmers has didn't provide enough profits on the hands of farmers to shop for two-time meals, neglect about the leisure of 24-hour power and water supply. To enhance situations of farmers, the authorities will have to emphasis on irrigation, improvement of rainfed agriculture, merchandising of integrated farming, excessive-price agri-produce, and many others. at the same time, diversification beyond vegetation into horticulture, greens, livestock, rooster and fisheries, etc followed with the aid of the improved investment in seeds can also be required. "similarly, the studies sector needs to be bolstered in order that incredible irrigation procedures may be advanced within the country itself. Greater centres for agricultural studies need to additionally be opened and college students want to be recommended to pursue profession paths of agricultural scientists. The government should additionally attract investments in agriculture so that scientific techniques can bolster the united states's crop manufacturing,"

KEYWORDS: A-Agriculture, I-Investment, M-Merchandising, H-Horticulture, T-Technique

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OP-90

IMPACT OF CYBER CRIME ON E-BANKING SYSTEM IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Net Banking or E-Banking refers back to the facility thru facts and conversation technology. net banking is increasingly more turning into popular day-to-day each comfort and versatility. pc fraudsters are usually trying to advantage unlawful get right of entry to day-to-day the facts of monetary and commercial enterprise day-to-day for fraudulent sports. The every day of net banking always fear for his or her monetary records whilst managing internet banking and its offerings. there may be a want every day create focus amongst net banking consumer on daily keep away from the available everyday threats. The research on this paper severely analyzes and discusses the outcomes of cyber threats whilst dealing with on-line banking services. it's far concluded that through the studies that there's a need every day growth protection measures in day-to-day cyber crimes when dealing with net banking and touchy monetary data.

KEYWORDS: C-Conversation, V-Versatility, F-Fraudsters, M-Monetary, P-Protection

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OP-91

THE ROLE OF CRITICAL THINKING IN EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Being a Teacher in 2024 is quite specific from being one in 2022. In a span of 10 years, the world of education has witnessed a sea change. As the arena keeps dealing with new demanding situations, specifically because of COVID-19, younger generations, and the training device they're part of, has also come to be dynamic. But, there are certain foundations to any schooling gadget that has stood the test of time. One key element that has constantly been confused upon and practiced through educators within the liberal schooling spectrum is presenting critical wondering talents. Improving a pupil's essential thinking talents is mainly critical in a liberal training version, which believes in teaching students how to assume and not what to think.

KEYWORDS- World of education, Younger generations, Talents. Improving Teaching students

Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur, UP

Digvijai Nath Post Graduate College, Gorakhpur was established on 25th August, 1969 by the managing committee constituted under Maharana Pratap Shiksha Parishad, Gorakhpur. It is situated in civil lines, the heart of Gorakhpur city in eastern Uttar Pradesh. Days are not far when the college shall be able to realize the vision and the grand mission of the great soul 'Brahmleen Mahant Digvijai Nath ji Maharaj', whose name decorates the identity of the College. His Holiness 'Brahmleen Mahant Digvijai Nath ji Maharaj, former Head Priest of world fame Shree Guru Goraksh Nath Temple, Gorakhpur was the founder of the college. He was a pioneer of educational renaissance in Eastern U.P. It was none other than himself who established Maha Rana Pratap Shiksha Parishad, Gorakhpur in 1932 to spread the light of knowledge and awareness among the people of Eastern U.P. whom he found to be living in utter poverty, ignorance and backwardness of all kinds. He came to Gorakhnath temple, Gorakhpur at the age of five from the Royal Rana Family of Mewar, Rajasthan in 1900 and grew and learnt the lesson of selfless sacrifice and dedication to the service of humanity under the spiritual care of his accomplished great Guru Yogiraj Gambhir Nathji Maharaj. In 1949-50 Maharana Pratap Degree College was established by "Maharana Pratap Shiksha Parishad Gorakhpur", which was later sacrificed to contribute to the establishment of Gorakhpur University. Maharana Pratap Degree College along with its entire infrastructure including teaching and non-teaching staff was dedicated to count for the resources to meet up the requirements for establishment of the University of Gorakhpur, in 1958. Post-merger of the Maharana Pratap Degree College into Gorakhpur University, there was a vacuum in the educational facilities of the area. To fill in this vacuum, Digvijai Nath College was established on 25th August 1969. Now the administration of this college is run by the managing committee appointed by Maharana Pratap Shiksha Parishad, Gorakhpur, under inspiring guidance and patronage of his Holiness Mahant Aditya Nath ji Maharaj. His holiness Gorakshpeethadheeshwar 'Brahmleen Mahant Avedya Nathji Maharaj (the Ex-Head priest of Gorakhnath Temple) and his worthy successor who is the Chief Minister of Uttar Pradesh His Holiness reverent Yogi Aditya Nath ji Maharaj, is the guiding light behind more than four dozen institutions, including D.N.P.G. College Gorakhpur, successfully run by the Maharana Pratap Shiksha Parishad. The College holds the glory of functioning with four faculty disciplines covering various departments at undergraduate and post graduate levels. College provides education at graduate level in eleven subjects covering Arts, six in Science and Commerce. Post Graduate teaching is offered in Ancient History Archeology & Culture, Geography and Hindi & Modern Indian Language; apart from its renowned Bachelors in Education. In addition to these, part time classes in eight non-practical subjects are also offered and the Institution also serves as an education center of Uttar Pradesh Rajarshi Tandon Open University; and hosts their 26 courses at U.G and P.G. level. In light of letter dated 15 June 2006 from U.P. State Council for Higher Education we revised 'The Self Study Report' on modified format on the basis of guidelines of NAAC-Bangalore. Digvijai Nath P.G. college, Civil lines, Gorakhpur has been placed on the UGC-NAAC approved list in 2021 with B++ grade with C.G.P.A 2.84. Gorakhnath sahyik kendra is established by UP Hindi Sansthan Lucknow in 2019. The institution, guided by the vision of Brahmleen Digvijai Nath Ji Maharaj, is a believer in multi-dimensional development of students.

Science-Tech Institute (Run By: Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society)

Science-Tech Institute (Run by: MKSES Educational Society, Lucknow)

The Science-Tech is one of the premier institutes of Lucknow dedicated to organize various academic activities like conferences, seminars, workshops and training programmes in collaboration with many National & International organizations. The Institute have own Publications house and Journals' to be published Edited books, Course books, research papers and Magazine. The institute is run by by reputed Educational Society named as Manraj Kuwar Singh Educational Society, Lucknow. The society is working for the development of deprived socio-economic students by providing them quality education. The society is devoted to provide quality education to the poor students in the field of academic and reserch.

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